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Determinants of Dividend Payout Ratio of Private Insurance Companies in Ethiopia

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Abstract:

Dividend is the pro-rata payment of money by firm to its shareholders usually on annual basis from generated income. Dividend policy which is controversial issue between firms and shareholders is a focal point of modern inquiry. To ascertain this debatable issue, this study examined the determinants of dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia by selected purposive eight private insurance companies from sixteen target population. The study used secondary source of quantitative data which were collected from audited annual financial report of each selected insurance companies and NBE during the period of 2007-2019. The collected data were analyzed using panel data random effect model with empirical outcomes that firm age, gross premium and lagged dividend have positive significant impact while leverage, growth opportunity and retained earnings have negative significant impact on dividend payout ratio. Profit and inflation rate have insignificant impact on dividend payout. The results implied that more aged firm and accumulate high premium income pays higher dividend whereas firm which is rapidly growing and more leveraged pay lower dividend.

Keywords: Determinants, Dividend Payout Ratio, Ethiopia, Private Insurance Companies.

INTRODUCTION

In modern era companies faced great dilemma on deciding whether distributing generated income to their shareholders as dividend or re-investing it back to foster further expansion of the business. When firm earns a profit, it creates the ability to re-invest the generated surplus or may distribute its proportion to pay dividend for shareholders. This distribution may be in the form of cash or issuing additional shares (Ross, Westerfield, & Jordan, 2003). In history of business world, Dutch East Company was the first ever company that paid regular dividend to its shareholders (Ahmed & Javid, 2009). Afterward, most companies in the world started to distribute a proportion of their income for shareholders with the thought that paying dividend is the way to satisfy their shareholders while other suggest that re-investing all portion of earnings to escalate companies' growth rate.

Hence, dividend decision is crucial issue that firm should determines how much earnings would be distributed to its shareholders, by what rate should it be distributed and amount to be retained for further business expansion (Watson & Head, 2010). Most firms used dividends as mechanism for financial signaling on stability of performance and growth prospects to the outsiders. Distributing more earnings as dividends will tend to increase the price of the stock while it lessens excess of money used for reinvestment (Tadele, 2017). Thus, dividend policy is a type of company decision that affects both the investors' and firms' wealth, and it decides the amount of payment ratio, which determines the amount and form of cash distributed to shareholders (Temesgen,

2016). As a result of this, for about six decades, dividend payout decision is a key study area in finance for investors, directors, financial analysts and academicians. As stated by (Muhammed, 2012), since the 1950's the effect of dividend policy on firm's value and other issues of corporate dividend payout decision become more subject of debate in both industrialized and developing business markets among many scholars.

The question why companies distribute dividend and companies' dividend policy is the center of investigation of modern business since the proposition of irrelevance theory developed by (Miller & Modigliani, 1961) put ground breaker in the theoretical modeling of dividends, dividend payment does not change shareholders' wealth. Afterward, several theories were developed to explain investors demand for dividends. In opposition to MM theory, bird in hand theory advocated that investors prefer dividend rather than expected capital gains. On the other hand, residual dividend theory stated that firm should distribute dividend to its shareholders only if there are no gainful investment opportunities (Myers & Majluf, 2013). Even though, extensive empirical research was carried out in this area, yet to date; no clear outcome on the main determinants of dividend payout policy of a firm and the way in which these factors are related to dividend.

In business world, insurance companies generate most of their income by charging premium on exchange of covering particular losses and perils. According to (Mashiur, Dipak, & Naznin, 2013) gross premium is one of the key determinant factors of dividend payout policy in insurance companies; by suggested that company which collects more premium will have excess cash flow that able to pay high dividend. Hence, this study fulfills the existing literature gap in Ethiopia by incorporating gross premium, which is not included in earlier studies, as additional explanatory variable. Besides to this, previous conducted studies had not encompassed the impact of retained earnings from firm-specific factors and inflation rate from macro-economic variables as determinants of dividend payout policy particularly in insurance companies. This study is not only added new variables, it also used comparatively long study period and collected more recent data than other previous study. Furthermore, since there is in consistence among existing literature, it requires further study by incorporating both insurance-specific and macro-economic variables.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of this study is to investigate the determinants of dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

After groundbreaking theory of dividend theory by MM, several theoretical and empirical studies about dividend payout policy of the companies were done by leading to the following main outcomes: -

Dividend Irrelevance Theory

This theory was developed by (Miller & Modigliani, 1961). As its name indicates it revealed that dividend policy of the firm cannot affect the firm value. In other word, dividend policy is irrelevance to firm value whether companies distribute or low dividend. According to these scholars, firm value is determined only by the earning capacity of the firm.

To check the proposition of MM irrelevance theory of dividend, (Black & Scholes, 1974) conducted study on association of dividend and stock price with come up with no relationship. At last, they

concluded dividend policy has no effect on firm value. In contrast to irrelevance theory, financial researchers and practitioners have disagreed with MM proposition and have argued that based the proposition of perfect capital market assumptions; assumptions that do not exist in real business world.

Pecking Order Theory

According to this theory, companies finance the new investment opportunity from their internal finance first and then if additional fund is required, they issue debt finance before equity finance to reduce transaction costs and information asymmetry costs (Myers & Majluf, 2013). The theory advocates that companies having high growth rate will generally experience high investment requirements and in turn will have lower payout ratio. In line to above, researchers (DeAngelo & Skinner, 2004) depicted that growth opportunities of a firm determines the dividend decision of a firm due to rapidly growing firms have a substantial need for funds to expand its investment opportunity instead of paying large amount of dividend.

Transaction Cost Theory

This theory states that firms having higher proportion of debt finance in total capital will have higher level of commitment to pay the fixed interest charges and this will reduce the dividend disbursement to equity shareholders (Higgins, 2011). When a firm raises capital from debt finance, it is committed to pay the fixed interest charge on the debt and the principal amount, in case of failure the firm has to undergo liquidation. Thus, the risk involved in the higher ratio of financial leverage will outcome in the lower dividend payment because holding other things constant, a firm requires the internally generated profit to pay the interest obligation rather than paying it to the common equity shareholders in form of dividends. According to (Al-Malkawi, Rafferty, & Pillai, 2010) firm that has high debt ratio pays few dividend because of it pays fixed payment, which reduce free cash flow, to service used from debt.

The "Bird-in the Hand" Theory

This theory was developed by (Gordon, 1959). It advocates that firm value is depending on the dividend which contrasts to the MM proposition. Their main expression is that "one bird in hand has more value than two in the bush". Expressed in financial terms, the theory says that investors are more willing to invest in stocks that pay current dividend rather than to invest in stocks that retain earnings and pay dividends in the future. Shortly, they advocated that "what you have on today is much worth than what you get on tomorrow". This is due to the high degree of uncertainty related to capital gains and dividends paid in the future (Gustav & Gairatjon, 2012). Hence, dividend is relevant to the value of the firm.

According to (Lintner, 1962) main arguments towards that the theory of bird in hand which is advocate of dividend is relevance to firm value is based on that most companies are conservative in their financing policy and the dividend payments are therefore, based on optimum payout ratio. The principal factor that contributes to deviations from optimum payout ratio is due changes in the company's profit, and if the profit increases the dividend payout should increase in the same proportions. However, uncertainty regarding future profits also has an impact on the company's dividends. If the estimated risk in the future is higher than the current risk, the company may decrease the dividend payout ratio.

The Life Cycle Theory

The theory was developed by (Mueller, 1972) stated that any firm has a well-defined life cycle and is fundamental to the firm life cycle theory of dividend. The mature firms have less investment opportunities, more accumulated profit and retained earnings that cause them to pay more dividends. In contrast to this, younger firms are in the stage of new growth opportunities and need to build reserves of profit to finance their growth opportunities that result in less dividend payment (DeAngelo & Skinner, 2004). Besides, scholars (Fama & French, 2007) concluded that big firm is further profitable and pay high dividend for their shareholders while small firm has no ease to access additional funds which needs for further growth opportunities; as a result it retain higher amount of their earnings.

Signaling Theory

This theory advocates the idea of dividend is used as the signal of information for external investors (Al-Malkawi, Rafferty, & Pillai, 2010). The signaling theory advocates that information asymmetry is there between the insider (managers) and outsiders (shareholders). The managers have secretive information about firm's current condition and future prospects which is not known to the outsiders. The managers can convey this private information to the shareholders in the form of dividend (Bhattacharya, 2007). Thus, dividend acts as signaling device and managers can receive incentives for communicating the private information to the outsiders. Hence, the investors have inferior signal information current and future about the companies.

Generally, during the last sixty years, a lot of empirical and theoretical work has been done regarding determinants of dividend policy. Based on the empirical review there are mixed results that indicate some factors of dividend payout policy of companies in a given country with secondary market, the same variable has different effect on dividend payout policy of firms in other countries' no secondary market. For instance, According to (Ahmed & Javid, 2009), (Henok, 2016) and (Muhammed, 2012) leverage was insignificant while it is negative significant according to (Milhem, 2016) whereas positive significant with dividend policy as per (Tadele, 2017). In addition to this, most study were contradicted on the result of growth opportunity variable; for instance, (Muhammed, 2012) and (Elias, 2015) stated growth opportunity has negative significant while (Henok, 2016) and (Chekole, 2016) opined positive significant whereas (Theodros, 2011) and (Temesgen, 2016) found out insignificant effect on dividend payout policy. These indicate that the conducted study was inconsistent throughout the study area and period. As result of this inconsistency, the researcher decided to look at main determinants of dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

METHODOLOGY

This section dealt with how this study was carried out. Explanatory research design was adopted because the study was sought the relationship between independent variables and dividend payout ratio. In addition to this, this study used quantitative research approach, which used for theory testing of relationship among variables.

The target population for this study was all 16 private insurance companies in Ethiopia (NBE, 2019). From this the researcher purposively selected 8 private insurance companies based on criteria of years of establishment and operation time. Secondary source of quantitative data of an audited financial statement of eight insurance companies (NICE, AWAIC, AFIC, NYALA, NILE, UNIC, GIC, NIB) for thirteen consecutive years from 2007-2019 inclusive were collected. Data of inflation rate were collected from national bank of Ethiopia (NBE). Therefore, the study employed

a time series data from the period 2007 up to 2019 for thirteen years and a cross sectional data of eight selected private insurance companies in Ethiopia with a balanced panel data of 104 (13*8) observations.

Based on this rational, the researcher used multiple linear regression models to examine the effect of explanatory variables on explained variable, dividend payout ratio.

General multiple linear regression model with many independent variables can be written as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_n X_{ni} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, t) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, Y represents dependent variable, β_0 represents the intercept, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_t$ represent the respective regression coefficients for explanatory variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n for estimating Y_{it} , ϵ it is the error term or disturbance that contains factors other than X_1, X_2, \dots, X_t that affect Y and subscript i denote the cross-sectional dimension (company) and t represent the time-series dimension (period).

Afterward theories mentioned above, the model has been specified as follows:

$$DPR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LEV_{it} + \beta_2 AGE_{it} + \beta_3 GOP_{it} + \beta_4 RE_{it} + \beta_5 GP_{it} + \beta_6 LDPR_{it} + \beta_7 PROF_{it} + \beta_8 INFR_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where;

- DPR_{it} = dividend payout ratio of insurance company i in period t,
- LEV_{it} = is debt ratio of insurance company i in period t,
- AGE_{it} = is age of insurance company i in period t,
- GOP_{it} = is growth opportunity of insurance company i in period t,
- RE_{it} = retained earnings amount of insurance company i at time t,
- GP_{it} = is gross premium of insurance company i in period t,
- $LDPR_{it}$ = is lagged dividend payout ratio paid by insurance company i in period t,
- $PROF_{it}$ = is return on equity of insurance company i in period t,
- $INFR_{it}$ = annual inflation rate at period t
- β_0 = is an intercept, β_t are the slope coefficients, ϵ_{it} is the error term

Variables Measurement

Based on above model development this section defined and developed the hypothesis for each explanatory variable.

Measure of Dividend Payout Ratio

Dividend payout ratio (DPR) is measured as the ratio of total annual dividend paid to the profit after tax (Henok, 2016) and (Amindu & Abor, 2006). Dividend is distributed amount from the profit of the insurance companies.

$$\text{Dividend payout ratio} = \frac{\text{annual dividend paid}}{\text{profit after interest and tax}}$$

Determinants of Dividend Payout Ratio

Leverage (LEV):

leverage of a company is proxied by the ratio of total debt to total asset. Based on existing literature the relationship between leverage and dividend payout policy of the firm is mixed. According to (Al-Malkawi, Rafferty, & Pillai, 2010) highly leveraged firm pays few dividends because of it pays fixed payment, which reduce free cash flow, to service used from debt. In addition to this, according to regulation insurance company that has high leverage ratio are under regulatory pressure which puts a restriction on paying high dividends (Muhammed, 2012) and found in line with agency cost theory which states firm that has low debt ratio pay more dividend whereas (Theodros, 2011) and (Henok, 2016) stated leverage is insignificant while (Tadele, 2017) positive significant on dividend payout ratio. Based on the above thought, the study hypothesized that there is negative relationship between leverage and dividend payout ratio.

Hypothesis 1: leverage has negative significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Age of Firm (AGE):

Companies that have been in business for so long period is positioned to have a good reputation for themselves as compared to companies with short period in business. Firms that have long duration in a world business have a good reputation which used for getting cheap credit to business expansion and in daily operation. According (De Angelo & Skinner, 2004) and (Temesgen, 2016), since old and aging firm have no further growing opportunities, it declare higher amount of its earning as dividend. Based on the above thought, there is positive correlation between age and dividend payout ratio.

Hypothesis 2: firm age has positive significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Growth Opportunity (GOP):

Companies having high growth opportunities require more money to finance their future investments, so that they pay fewer dividends and make more investments (Myers & Majluf, 2013). Therefore, there is inverse relationship between growth opportunity of the company and dividend payout ratio. A proxy for the growth opportunity is calculated as the ratio of current revenue minus previous revenue to previous revenue. Hence based on the above theoretical and empirical theory, study hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 3: growth opportunity has significant negative impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Retained earnings (RE):

Company retained its earnings for the purpose of business expansion and to capture investment opportunity, so funds from its annual profit every year retained in amount decided by boards. Based on theoretical viewpoint, amount retained from income of the firm decreases amount distributed to shareholders. Previous scholars like (Onail, 2009) and (Huda & Farah, 2011) and (Tadele, 2017) found a negative correlation between retained earnings and dividend payout. Hence based on the empirical review, study hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 4: A retained earnings has negative significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Gross premium (GP):

Is the income of insurance company which collected from the insured persons and companies throughout a year. Since it is a part of company's earnings, a company that generate high amount of premium will pay high amount of dividend to its shareholders. (Mashiur, Dipak, & Naznin, 2013) found there is positive and statistically significant between gross premium and dividend payout. Hence, based on this certainty, the study expected a direct relationship between gross premium and dividend payout ratio of insurance companies. It is proxied by the ratio of total underwriting income to total asset of the company. Hence based on the above empirical theory, study hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 5: gross premium has positive significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Lagged dividend (LDPR):

It is a dividend distributed in previous year. In real business world most firms use previous year dividend as blueprint for current year by on to increase payout ratio. This indicates, there is positive link with current dividend payout which in line with signal theory when companies wants to give a positive signal to the market, that company is in good condition whereby it is continuing paying dividends. Scholars like (Elias, 2015), (Rehman & Takumi, 2012), (Nsikan, Ataire, & Francis, 2014), (Henok, 2016) and (Tadele, 2017) found positive relationship between last year dividends and current year payout ratio. Therefore, based on this discussion, the study hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 6: A previous lagged dividend has positive significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Profitability (PROF):

Is used to measure how shareholders fared during the year, which is net earnings divided to the value of shareholders' equity. (Lintner, 1962) found that the critical factor affecting the dividend decision of a firm is the net earnings. In another study, (Fama & French, 2007), (Henok, 2016) and (Tadele, 2017) found that the larger and more profitable firms pay more dividends as compared to smaller and fewer profitable firms as the dividends are paid from the profit after tax. Therefore, the study expects profitability has direct associated with amount of dividend payout ratio. It is proxied by the ratio of income after interest and taxes to shareholders' capital.

Hypothesis 7: Profit has positive significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Annual Inflation rate (INFR):

As stated by (Ghafoor, Asif, Asim, & Hussain, 2014) when inflation of one's country becomes elevated, most firms usually retain a huge part of their earnings to avoid a drop in their balance of operation and to recompense for the reduction in purchasing power of money. Hence, the firm would not be interested to pay much dividend for their shareholders. Hence regarding to above reality, researcher expected that inflation rate and dividend payout would have opposite relationship. In contrast to above thought, investors on their side would enthusiast for high

amount of dividend in line for the fall in purchasing power of the currency during inflation (Basse & Reddemann, 2011). (Duncan & Wairimu, 2013) found positive relationship while (Nsikan et al, 2014) found a negative relationship between inflation and dividend payout. Research conducted in Ethiopia by (Tadele, 2017) found there is negative relationship between inflation rate and dividend policy. Based on the above-mentioned discussion, researcher hypothesized that:

Hypothesis 8: Inflation rate has negative significant impact on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Here below table summarizes the determinants of payout ratio and their expected relationship with dividend payments.

Table 3.1: Measurement and expected sign of the study variables

	Variables	Measurement	Empirical Evidence	Expected sign
Dependent variable	Dividend payout ratio	$\frac{\text{Annual dividend paid}}{\text{net income after tax and legal reserve}}$	(Amindu & Abor, 2006) and (Henok, 2016)	
Independent variables	Leverage	$\frac{\text{Total liability}}{\text{total asset}}$	(Dickens, 2002) and (Henok, 2016)	-
	Firm age	Difference between year of establishment and corresponding study year.	(Temesgen, 2016)	+
	Growth opportunity	$\frac{\text{Current year revenue}-\text{previous year}}{\text{previous year revenue}}$	(Theodros, 2011) and (Henok, 2016)	-
	Retained earnings	$\frac{\text{Retained income after dividend}}{\text{Income after tax and interest}}$	(Huda & Farah, 2011) and (Tadele, 2017)	-
	Lagged dividend	$\frac{\text{Previous year dividend}}{\text{previous year income after tax and legal reserve}}$	(Rehman & Takumi, 2012) and (Elias, 2015)	+
	Gross premium	$\frac{\text{Income from underwriting}}{\text{total asset}}$	(Mashiur, Dipak, & Naznin, 2013)	+
	Profitability (ROE)	$\frac{\text{Earning before tax and legal reserve}}{\text{shareholders' equity}}$	(Henok, 2016)	+
	Inflation rate	Annual Inflation rate of the country	(Tadele, 2017)	-

Source: compiled by researcher, 2019

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section analyzes and discusses the main findings of the study, in comparison to the theories and empirical results earlier discussed and presented in previous sections, by using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Furthermore, the stated hypotheses are carefully discussed in this section.

Thus, the developed model is:

$$DPR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1LEV_{it} + \beta_2AGE_{it} + \beta_3GOP_{it} + \beta_4RE_{it} + \beta_5GP_{it} + \beta_6LDPR_{it} + \beta_7PROF_{it} + \beta_8INFR_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

The coefficients of explanatory variable were estimated by the use of OLS technique. The regression result in Table 4.1 demonstrates explanatory variables with their coefficients and corresponding p-values.

Table 4.1: result of regression, Hausman- random effects model

Random-effects GLS regression		Number of obs = 104				
Group variable: code		Number of groups = 8				
R-sq: within = 0.5726		Obs per group: min = 13				
Between = 0.4065		avg = 13.0				
Overall = 0.5413		max = 13				
		Wald chi2(8) = 112.09				
corr(u_i, X) = 0 (assumed)		Prob > chi2 = 0.0000				
Dpr	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
lev	-.5506878	.2316355	-1.38	0.017**	-1.004685	-.0966905
age	.027423	.0056415	1.86	0.000*	.0163658	.0384801
gop	-.0958083	.0415887	-1.30	0.021**	-.1773206	-.0142961
re	-.3108247	.0796077	-1.90	0.000*	-.466853	-.1547965
Gp	.8682347	.3010554	1.88	0.004*	.278177	1.458292
ldpr	.1700077	.073761	1.30	0.021**	.0254388	.3145766
Prof	.0965845	.0751286	1.29	0.199	-.0506649	.2438338
infr	-.0052832	.1608665	-0.03	0.974	-.3205757	.3100093
_cons	.5101072	.1599832	1.19	0.001	.1965459	.8236684

*and** denoted significance at 1% and 5% respectively. Source: STATA output

Regression result in table 4.9 shows that leverage, growth opportunity, retained earnings and inflation rate have negative coefficient whereas firm age, gross premium, lagged dividend and profitability have positive coefficient toward dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Based on the regression analysis result in table 4.9, the relationship between the variables included in the model can, therefore, be represented as follows to examine dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia:

$$DPR = 0.51 - 0.551LEV + 0.0274AGE - 0.096GOP - 0.311RE + 0.868GP + 0.17LDPR + 0.097PROF - 0.0053INFR$$

Based on result from table 4.9, Probability>F= 0.0000 which is statistically significant at 1% indicates the overall model is good fitted to explain dependent variable. The coefficient of determination of R2 good fitness of model is 0.5726 means 57.26% of variations in dividend payout ratio of dividend payout ratio is explained by LEV, AGE, GOP, RE, GP, LDPR, PROF and INFR while the remaining 42.7% were wavered by other variables that are not incorporated in the model, including the error term.

As depicted in the table 4.9, the coefficient estimate of the constant of the regression (β_0) is 0.51 shows that all other value of explanatory variables becomes zero or if all variables excluded from

the model; the value of explained variable (dividend payout) is increased by 0.51 with statistically significant at 1% level of significance with p-value of 0.001.

After careful investigation of factors determining dividend payout ratio of insurance companies the following conclusions are made based on regression results.

Based on regression analysis result, the relationship between dividend payout ratio and leverage is in line with pecking order theory which stated that negative correlation between these two variables. This recognizes that negative relationship between dividend payout ratio and leverage was recognized to the fact that; private insurance companies in Ethiopia obligated to have excess cash flow which used to pay outstanding claim against unexpected loss on insured persons. Hence, higher proportion of profit of highly leveraged companies was used to cover obligations of financing cost which leads to decrease dividend payout ratio.

In line with developed hypothesis and life cycle theory, the result shows that the effect of firm age has positive significant effects on dividend payout ratio. Stand upon the result, researcher concluded that the more aged companies have excess accumulated earnings and less growth opportunity which leads to pay high dividend, as compared to growing companies.

On other hand, according to the results there is a significant negative relationship between growth opportunities of the insurance companies with their dividend payment. In their financial report, some insurance companies capitalize dividend declared for ripe growing opportunity and further internal expansion. This finding in line with pecking order theory which states that the companies should be more focuses internal development before distributing dividend. From the above regression result, the negative significant relationship of growth with dividend indicate that private insurance companies in Ethiopia are in growing stage and more focused on prospect of future. It revealed the firms that have higher growth opportunities have a tendency to retain their earnings for future investments, and further focused on internal expansion, hence, that they pay fewer dividends.

There was a significant negative link between retained earnings and dividend payout decision; due to growing companies will prefer to use income as internal source of fund for expansion of their business. Since most of insurance companies in Ethiopia are rapidly growing, their financial requirements are high which leads to retain earnings; and therefore, the amount of dividend distributed is reduced.

Based on regression analysis result, dividend payout of insurance companies reacts positively towards increasing of gross premium collected from underwritten. The relationship is as expected which implies; as the revenue collected from insured companies increases, the generated fund also increases proportionally which able to pay high dividend to shareholders.

Based on regressed data outcomes, lagged dividend has significant positive impact on current dividend payout ratio which is in line with signaling theory. From the above regression result, it revealed that high previous year dividend payment serve as indication for future expectation about payment of high current year dividend payment. However, such a dividend disbursement behavior supports the idea of smooth dividend payout ratio model proposed by (Lintner, 1962); private insurance companies in Ethiopia do not follow any type of dividend payout ratio. The main reason behind paying high dividend is to keep their goodwill and indicator of profitable

companies. Additionally, this research concluded that companies want to get a positive indicator to seem on a good condition for attracting of potential investors by continues paying dividend and also due to high inflation that deteriorate the purchasing power of currency may leads insurance companies to pay better dividend in every year on basis of the previous year dividend.

In contrast to developed hypothesis, profitability has positive insignificant relationship with dividend payout ratio. The study concludes that main reason why profitability is positively insignificant with dividend payout ratio is, most insurance companies are only focused on reaching the bounds of maximum market share by reinvesting the gained earnings rather than distributing more dividends to their shareholders. Besides this, the researcher calls for further studies.

Lastly, researcher give a picture of the effects of inflation rate on dividend payout decision with the result of negative insignificant correlation which implied that inflation of the country has not much effect on dividend payout ratio of private insurance companies in Ethiopia. The study concluded by giving suggestion of due to NBE to stabilize inflation across the country, and this lead to no effects on both companies and investors of private insurance companies in Ethiopia.

Based on the above regression analysis results, the study concludes in below table 4.10 the summary of regression analysis results with compared to expected results earlier.

Table 4.2: Comparison of actual result with expectation

Hypothesis (HP)	Independent Variables	Expected Sign with DPR	Actual Result	Decision
HP1	Leverage	-ve & sig	-ve & sig	Fail to reject at 5%
HP2	Firm age	+ve & sig	+ve & sig	Fail to reject at 5%
HP3	Growth opportunity	-ve & sig	-ve & sig	Fail to reject at 5%
HP4	Retained earnings	-ve & sig	-ve & sig	Fail to reject at 5%
HP5	Gross premium	+ve & sig	+ve & sig	Fail to reject at 5%
HP6	Lagged dividend	+ve & sig	+ve & sig	Fail to reject at 5%
HP7	Profitability	+ve & sign	+ve & insig	Reject at 5%
HP8	Inflation rate	-ve & sig	-ve & insig	Reject at 5%

CONCLUSIONS

Generally, the empirical outcomes advocated that variable like leverage, growth opportunity, retained earnings and inflation rate have negatively moved while variables like firm age, gross premium, lagged dividend and profit have positively moved dividend payout ratio. This indicates that more aged firms and generate more income from premium pay higher dividend ratio whereas firms which have higher growth opportunity and highly leveraged have lower dividend payout ratio. From the regression analysis researcher found that all the variables except profitability and inflation rate are statistically significant with dividend payout decision during the period of 2007-2019. As seen from results, the findings are in line with the transaction cost, pecking order, the life cycle and signaling theory of dividend payout decision and found little suggestion for thought of (Lintner, 1962) which opined more profitable firm pays high dividend which requires further studies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on obtained results, the study recommends that board of directors and managers of insurance companies will focus on gross premium, leverage and retained earnings that are significantly affects dividend payout ratio. Moreover, the investors also give main attention to these variables and firm age; while selecting their investment area specifically in insurance companies. In addition to this, only 57% of dividend behavior of insurance companies was explored by this study, the remaining 43% are explained by other firm specific and macroeconomic variables which were not included in this study. Hence, researcher recommends future academicians to undertake similar study by in view of additional firm specific (like; financial efficiency, EPS, MBV ratio and free cash flow) and macroeconomic variables (like; GDP and exchange rate). Additionally, further recommendable area is analyzing dividend payout behavior across industries by incorporating different industries like insurance, cement factory, banks, construction companies and other share companies. As a final point, the study recommends further scholars to investigate study by using another proxy method for variables.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, H., & Javid, A. Y. (2009). Determinants of Dividend Policy in Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 110- 125.
- Al-Malkawi, H., Rafferty, M., & Pillai, R. (2010). Dividend Policy: A Review of Theories and Empirical Evidence. *International Bulletin of Business Administration*, 9(1), 109-132.
- Amindu, M., & Abor, J. (2006). Determinants of the Dividend payout ratio in Ghana. *The Journal of Risk Finance*, 7(2), 132-145.
- Basse, T., & Reddemann, S. (2011). Inflation and the dividend policy of US firms. *Managerial Finance*, 37(1), 93-122.
- Bhattacharya, S. (2007). Imperfect Information, Dividend Policy, and "the Bird in the Hand" Fallacy. *Bell Journal of Economics*, 10, 259-270.
- Chekole, Y. (2016). Internal Determinants of Dividend Payout in Private Commercial Banks in Ethiopia. Master Thesis submitted to in Accounting and Finance, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- DeAngelo, H., & Skinner, D. (2004). Are dividends disappearing? Dividend concentration and the consolidation of earnings. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 72, 425-456.
- Duncan, O. E., & Wairimu, M. E. (2013). Relationship between Inflation and Dividend payout for companies listed at the Nairobi securities exchange. *international Journal of Education and Research*, 1(6), 123-145.
- Elias, M. (2015). Determinants of Dividend payout of Ethiopian private banks. masters graduate thesis, Addis ababa, Ethiopia.
- Fama, F., & French, K. (2007). Disappearing dividends: Changing firm characteristics or lower propensity to pay. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3-43.
- Gordon, M. (1959). Dividends earnings, and stock prices. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 41(2), 99-105.
- Gustav, H., & Gairatjon, I. (2012). Determinants of Dividend Payout Ratios; A Study of Swedish Large and Medium Caps. A degree projects.
- Henok, T. (2016). Internal factors influencing dividend payout of Ethiopian insurance companies. graduate research thesis of accounting and finance, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Higgins, R. C. (2011). The corporate dividend-saving decision. *Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, 7(2), 1527-1541.

- Huda, F., & Farah, T. (2011). Determinants of Dividend Decision: A Focus on Banking Sector in Bangladesh. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics (Issue 77)*, 33-46.
- Lintner, J. (1962). Distribution of Incomes of Corporations among Dividends, Retained Earnings, and Taxes. *The American Economic Review*, 46(2), 97-113.
- Mashiur, R., Dipak, K. D., & Naznin, S. C. (2013). Determinants of Dividend Payouts: Study on the Insurance Sector of Bangladesh. *Journal of Research of Economics*, 1-20.
- Miller, M. H., & Modigliani, F. (1961). Dividend Policy, Growth, and the Valuation of Shares. *Journal of Business*, 34(4), 411-433.
- Mueller, D. C. (1972). A life cycle theory of the firm. *The Journal of Industrial Economics*, 20(3), 199–219.
- Muhammed, N. (2012). Determinants of Dividend Policy of Insurance Companies in Ethiopia. Graduate Thesis, Addis Ababa university, Ethiopia.
- Myers, S. C., & Majluf, N. S. (2013). Corporate Financing and Investment Decisions When Firms Have Information that Investors Do Not Have. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 13, 187-221.
- NBE. (2019). National Bank of Ethiopia Annual report. Addis Ababa Ethiopia: NBE. Retrieved Aug 05, 2019, from www.nbe.gov.et.
- Nsikan, B. E., Ataire, E. A., & Francis, A. A. (2014). Determinants of dividend payout of financial institutions in Nigeria: A study of selected commercial banks. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5, 123-142.
- Onail, E. (2009). Dividends and Risk in European banks. <http://studys.ssrn.com/sol3/studys.cfm?>
- Rehman, A., & Takumi, R. (2012). Determinants of dividend payout ratio: Evidence from Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE). *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business Research*, 1(1), 20-27.
- Ross, S., Westerfield, R., & Jordan, B. (2003). *Fundamentals of Corporate Finance (Vol.2 6th ed.)*. New York, USA: The McGraw–Hill Companies.
- (SIB/38/2014). Supervision of insurance business directive SIB/38/2014. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Tadele, T. (2017). Determinants of dividend policy In Ethiopian private banks. Graduate thesis submitted to Accounting and Finance, Addis Ababa University. Ethiopia.
- Temesgen, y. (2016). Determinants of Corporate Dividend Payout: In Case of Ethiopian Private Insurance Share Companies. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7(15).
- Theodros, K. (2011). Determinants of dividend payout: An emperical study on Banking industry in Ethiopia. Post graduate thesis submitted to Accounting and Finance departement, Addis Ababa University. Ethiopia.
- Watson, D., & Head, A. (2010). *Corporate Finance: Principles & Practice (5th ed.)*. Pearson Education Limited. USA.

The Economic and Social Impacts of Chewing Khat among Youths in Dambi Dollo, Kellem Wollega Zone, Ethiopia

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Abstract:

Ethiopia is thought to be the origin of khat and currently, it is consumed everywhere in the country mainly by youths (Andualem, 2002). The purpose of this study was to identify the economic and social effects of chewing khat among youths of Dambi Dollo town. The study was designed as cross-sectional descriptive and to achieve the purpose of the study we employed an exponential snowball sampling technique by which 384 sampled respondents were invited to fill the questionnaires mixed with an interview. The descriptive statistics showed that out of the total youths chewing khat in the town, during the survey, the majority of them were single males (87%), Christian in religion (48%), college graduates and above, and originally born in rural, on average. Accordingly, we have investigated that frequent khat chewing, chewing outside of the home, using additional substances, using khat for recreation, and being absent from the job for khat sessions were factors that are associated with the negative economic effect of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town and their families. Related to this, low saving culture, debt, decreased family budget, dependency, wastage of time and unemployment are the negative impacts of chewing khat among youths in the study area. Whereas moderate consumption of khat for work purposes which results in the accomplishment of activities efficiently and confidently was identified as a major positive economic impact of chewing khat among youths in the study area. In addition, social exclusion, reduced family time and divorce were major identified negative social effects of chewing khat among the youths. Therefore, we recommend that all concerned bodies have to intervene by creating awareness of the negative consequences of frequent khat chewing on society and the economy, more job opportunities for employment, investing in urban youths through training, and sports, preparing a public lecture, and learning about the negative economic and social impacts of frequent khat consumption khat for youths and community competitions packaged with economic incentives among others were highly recommended.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Khat (*Catha edulis* Forssk) is an evergreen flowering tree or shrub, first identified by Forsskal, abotanistin1762. It's mainly cultivated in East Africa and the Arabian Peninsula. Ethiopia is thought to be the origin of khat and currently, it is consumed everywhere in the country mainly by youths (Andualem, 2002). Khat originated in Ethiopia and spread through Kenya, Somalia, Djibouti, Uganda, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Zambia, South Africa, and Yemen (Gebisa, 2010).

Ethiopia is thought to be the origin of khat and currently, it is consumed everywhere in the country mainly by youth. Khat is a leafy shrub planted mostly in the northeastern parts of Africa, including Ethiopia. Khat leaves and buds contain the alkaloid cathinone, a stimulant, which is said to cause excitement, loss of appetite, and euphoria (Carrier and Klantsching, 2018).

Globally, the khat chewing practice is becoming alarming and common among the youth generation. The estimate of the number of people chewing khat globally ranges from 5 to 10 million people. Chewing khat has been practiced in many countries for social, cultural, social psychological, and religious reasons (Yeshialem, 2013).

Like many other countries, khat chewing for social and psychological reasons has been practiced in Ethiopia for centuries; and its use has been gradually expanded worldwide (Yeshigeta and Abraham, 2004; Ezekiel, 2005; Wabel, 2011). But until a few decades, khat chewing in Ethiopia was mainly limited to older men and members of Muslim communities.

Recently, khat chewing becomes a common practice among high school, College, and University students. Students have consumed khat to be alert and wakeful at night; especially during examination periods. Moreover, they used it as a recreational substance. Among undergraduate medical students of Addis Ababa University; 14% of the participants chewed khat. In Dire Dawa high school, 18.4% of students chewed khat. Similarly, other sections of the community; such as laborers, truck drivers, craftsmen, teachers, and farmers have chewed khat to reduce fatigue, increase performance, and suppress appetite. In Jimma town, 37.8% of the communities reported khat chewing practices (Zemenu and Tadele, 2019).

However recent trends indicated its consumption of large quantities has become a pastime activity and far reached large members of the population resulting in serious consequences on their health and socio-economic conditions (Ashbury, 2005; Dawit et al 2005). Khat chewing may harm the economy by the loss of production as a result of laziness and absenteeism. Workers go to lunch and engage in Khat sessions, and do not return to work. A current estimate suggests that over 10 billion hours of work a year were lost as a result of the Khat habit (Muluneh 2018). It may also lead to frequent misbehavior, poor economic, social and academic performance, and memory impairment among youths (Tsegaye et al, 2019). With these realities, khat is now a controversial crop to the world in general; and to Ethiopians in particular.

For instance, by accounting for 13.4% of the export earnings, khat is the third largest export crop, next to coffee and oil seed. Hence, it plays a considerable role not only in the national economy, but also it is a major income source for millions of farming households, and traders who directly or indirectly depend on it (Aden et al, 2006; Bongard et al, 2011).

In general, there is a lack of consensus on the impact of the production and consumption of khat. Some argue that khat is an essential crop as it stimulates people to work for long hours through increased concentration (Gebissa, 2010). They also emphasize the importance of khat in generating foreign exchange and creating employment opportunities (Gebissa, 2004; Klein, 2010). On the contrary, Beckerleg (2010) and Branko (2008) argue that khat is an addictive substance with possible negative consequences. They believe that khat use makes users careless, less accountable, and irresponsible, thereby increasing social crime. In addition, they indicate that khat takes a significant share of the daily expenditure of regular users and hence diverts money away from productive activities. For this reason, they favor strict government control on the production and distribution of the khat plant.

Statement of the Problem

The available research on khat tends to provide polarized perspectives. There is a debate about whether khat consumption habit has a negative or positive impact on the economy as well as if

that is a barrier or facilitator to development and poverty alleviation in the country (Cochrane and Negash, 2017).

On the one hand, there is a group of scholars like (Mekuria et al, 2018) who hold that khat chewing leads to a loss of work hours, divorce, decreased economic productivity, malnutrition, and diversion of money to buy further khat. This group also indicates that khat is linked to absenteeism and unemployment, which may, in turn, result in a decline in overall national economic productivity. This group of scholars tends to also highlight the negative health impacts of khat (Reda et al, 2012). This group of researchers paid more attention to the negative social and economic impacts of chewing khat. However, this study will examine both negative and positive social and economic impacts of chewing khat among youths in the study area.

On the other hand, scholars like (Gebisa, 2008) hold that khat has positive outcomes, such as increasing peaceful social coexistence, improving social connectivity and even health, promoting productivity, and when consumed "moderately", improving performance and increasing work output because it stimulates and postpones fatigue. Consequently, working hours, and possibly productivity, are suggested to decrease when khat is not used because of reduced motivation. Concerning khat cultivation and production, this group of scholars points out that khat cultivation doubles the income of farmers and boosts their income and general living standards (Gebisa, 2012).

Khat chewing has a deep-rooted socio-cultural tradition, its pleasure-inducing, and stimulating effects seemingly having a strong influence on the social and cultural life of the communities who indulge in it. Khat chewing has a deep-rooted socio-cultural tradition, its pleasure-inducing, and stimulating effects seemingly having a strong influence on the social and cultural life of the communities who indulge in it (Lamina, 2010). Khat sessions are occasions for the exchange of information, and discussions on plans and decisions for communities in Yemen and central and eastern parts of Ethiopia. It is also culturally very significant that khat sessions are held during cultural functions like birth, circumcision, and marriage. People also use it as an enhancer to carry out their daily activities. Laborers chew khat during hard physical work, students when preparing for exams, and lorry drivers for long-distance travel to increase their level of concentration. Special khat sessions are also organized by clan elders and judges to settle disputes and court cases Lamina (2010). Khat is therefore used both in social and formal settings and its main function is a communal one, stimulating sociability (Anderson et al, 2007).

Although these scholars have investigated the positive social and economic impacts of chewing khat, they have overemphasized the positive contributions of chewing khat by implying that working motivation, social gatherings, and sociability of the chewers as it solely depends on chewing. However, the social and economic impacts of chewing khat among youths in different regions of Ethiopia may vary from zone to zone, woreda to woreda, and town to town.

Even though few studies have been conducted in different parts of Ethiopia in general and some, a study was not conducted in the study area to the level of our knowledge. In addition to this, the researchers mentioned above have investigated controversial ideas on the social and economic impacts of chewing khat among different sections of society. Therefore, we are motivated to assess the social and economic impacts of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town.

Research Questions:

Based on the above-identified problems, we were motivated to answer the following questions.

- What are the social impacts of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town?
- What are the economic impacts of chewing khat on youths in Dambo Dollo town?

Objectives of the Study

General Objective of the Study:

The overall objective of this study was to assess the social and economic effects of chewing khat among the youths in Dambi Dollo town.

Specific Objectives of the Study:

The specific objectives of this study were as follows;

- To assess the social effects of chewing khat among the youths in Dambi Dollo town
- To analyze the economic effects of chewing khat among the youths in Dambi Dollo town

Significances of the Study

For countries like Ethiopia, the issue of khat is national agenda. Khat provides different job opportunities for millions of people engaged in the production and marketing of the product and it is the highest export-earning product next to coffee and oil seeds ((Aden et al, 2006; Bongard et al, 2011). While this is a very positive contribution to the economy, domestic consumption has increased very rapidly, and many scholars were concerned with its effects on the health and productivity of the workforce. Currently, tens of millions of people consume khat. Unfortunately, the impact of its domestic use has not been widely studied.

This study would be significant in three ways. Firstly, it will make its modest contribution to filling the gap in knowledge by assessing the social and economic impacts of khat chewing among the youths of Dambi Dollo town. Both the positive and negative impacts of khat chewing will be discussed. Secondly, consumption has become a culture in some parts of Ethiopia, and the major consumers are at their most productive age. The study, therefore, will give some indication of how far the consumption of khat affects/promotes the social and economic development of the town and further the country. Thirdly, the Ethiopian government neither promotes nor discourages the production and consumption of khat. This may be partly due to the significant economic contributions of khat to the country and partly due to the lack of sufficient empirical findings on its potentially adverse and long-term socio-economic impacts. This study will contribute its part to the little research which has been done.

Scope of the Study

This study was geographically limited to covering Dambi Dollo town and the findings might not give a full picture of the practice in other parts of the zone. Conceptually, it focused on the social and economic impacts of khat chewing among the youths in Dambi Dollo town. Methodologically, the study employed a cross-sectional research design in which both qualitative and quantitative research approaches have been used.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Origin and Definition of Khat

The earliest reference to this plant appears to be dated around 973–1053 AD by Al-Biurni, who meticulously compiled information on all contemporary drugs, what he called qat that was imported from Turkistan. It was used to relieve biliousness and to cool the stomach and liver. Hancock and Forrest (1974) mentioned that it is possible to find a referral to khat as early as 1332 AD in an Arabic manuscript preserved in the Biblioteque National in Paris. Some scholars have

written that its use was prevalent in Ethiopia and from there, around the fifteenth century, the practice spread to the southwest of the Arabian Peninsula. Arab sources suggested that khat was in Yemen in the sixth century when the Ethiopians conquered Yemen (Dhaifalaha et al, 2004).

Khat (*Catha edulis* Forsk) is botanically classified under the family Celastraceae. Chat grows primarily in East Africa and the Arabian Peninsula. Ethiopia is the country of its origin and it is the world's largest khat producer; where a khat chewing habit was started in the 15th century, just before the start of the use of coffee. The crop now grows well at higher altitudes in the Horn of Africa and the Arabian Peninsula where khat chewing has a long history as a social custom dating back thousands of years. By now there are more than 10 million people in the world who uses khat daily for its euphorizing and psycho-stimulant effect (Andualem, 2002; Bongard et al, 2011).

An overview of Khat Consumption

Khat is a leafy shrub planted mostly in the northeastern parts of Africa, including Ethiopia. Khat leaves and buds contain the alkaloid cathinone, a stimulant, which is said to cause excitement, loss of appetite, and euphoria (Carrier & Klantschnig, 2018). It is "chewed" or held within the mouth while absorption takes place (typically only the "juices" are swallowed, not the leaves). Khat consumption or chewing is a habit of chewing khat frequently and encountering symptoms of withdrawal when consumption is skipped or missed. Khat culture is the widespread consumption of khat in a given community, which is a growing trend now in Harar. It is community-level khat consumption where every group of people chews khat, like in Harar (Abere, et al, 2020).

In Harar, khat is used not only for entertainment but also for more serious businesses like religion and work, and they accepted it as an integral part of their culture. Khat culture also involves the ceremony of chewing khat. This culture develops over a long period. Written evidence shows that khat chewing started in Harar before the 19th century (Burton, 1856). One of my informants said, "This is the culture that we inherited from our grand grandfathers." Khat chewer or consumer, in this study, refers to a person who uses khat at least two or three times a week and feels uncomfortable, bored and displays unusual behavior including depressive mood, irritability, anorexia, and difficulty sleeping and mood swings when not consuming or finding khat (ECDD, 2006). People in Harar called this feeling Haraara.

Concerning consumption, it is important to note that khat chewing has a long history in the Horn of Africa. Reports of khat use in the hinterlands of the Horn of Africa go back at least eight centuries. The leaves were chewed by the people in the medieval Islamic sultanates of the southern region of today's Ethiopia as early as the fourteenth century. From there, the chew culture spread to the Horn region along the historic long-distance trading routes that connected Muslim trading states and with the Indian Ocean world. By the mid-nineteenth century, the plant was used for a variety of purposes in the region that is now Ethiopia. In the Kingdom of Shawa (central Ethiopia) and Kaffa (southwestern Ethiopia) the plant was extensively cultivated and used (Beke, 1843, and Harris, 1844,). In the Tigray region in the north, khat was used for enhancing the flavor of a local drink made of honey (Férret and Galinier, 1848).

In eastern Ethiopia, specifically in the Harer highlands, khat consumption had assumed the chew features that are a quite familiar today (Moktar, 1876; Burton, 1966,). Beginning in the early twentieth century, its consumption was transformed from a luxury enjoyed by the urban elite to a cultural practice performed by a significant portion of the population in the region and, after the

1930s, to a commonplace pastime activity of nearly all social classes, cultural categories, and religious affiliations. Today, regional and countrywide surveys reveal that an average of 30 percent of Ethiopians are regular khat chewers (Belew et al, 2000; Arrafaine, 2004).

By the late nineteenth century, khat chewing must have been so widespread in Zeyla that Sayid Mahamed Abdille Hasan, the Somali nationalist leader, and poet, condemned the members of the Sufi Order in the town for promoting the leaves as a plant that Allah revealed to the faithful to help them stay awake for prayer during the month of Ramadan (Hassan, 2001). The level of consumption must have reached a critical point obliging British authorities of the Somaliland Protectorate to pass a law in 1921 forbidding the cultivation, import, and sale of khat (Elmi, 1984). In 1936, official reports show the Somaliland Protectorate imported 4000 bundles (approximately 4000 kg) of khat, in addition to the amount smuggled across the border to evade the restriction imposed by the British ban (Gesheker, 1985).

During the Second World War, khat consumption not only increased in the border towns but also extended deep into the protectorate owing to the connection by modern transportation of the Protectorate with the khat-producing areas of the Harerge highlands and the migration of a considerable number of Somali pastoralists to urban centers. By 1945, according to the estimate of the British consul in Harer, about 3000 kg of khat were smuggled daily into the Protectorate (Gebissa, 2004).

In southern Somalia, the existing literature suggests that khat consumption was virtually unknown before the Second World War. It is said that local customs prohibited khat use and Italian authorities strictly enforced a law they had promulgated, often by burning khat they found in the territory. The fact that the Italians had to resort to scorching tactics indicates the use of khat here had a more longstanding history than previously acknowledged. When the British took control of all of the Somali territories in 1941, the process of integration of the two territories was initiated, thereby making business and cultural exchange possible. In the 1950s, khat chewing spread to southern Somalia as more and more Somalis took up the habit as an act of defiance against colonial authority (Gesheker, 1985). In the 1960s, independence and integration of the former Italian and Ethiopian colonial territories allowed for the khat chewing habit to flow southward unencumbered. Within two decades, khat reportedly became the dominant feature in all walks of life. By the early 1980s, khat chewing had become a significant part of the social fabric of Somali society and a catalyst for communication, conviviality, and commerce (Hassan, 2001). The importance of khat is reflected in the fact that in 1983 Somalia spent \$57 million, an amount equivalent to 5.7 percent of the GDP, on importing khat (Elmi, 1984). In Djibouti khat has been consumed since the creation of the port in 1869. At the time, the chewers were mostly Yemeni Arabs who, from the founding of the port, constituted a substantial element of the city's population. For Yemeni Arabs, khat chewing had been a long-standing and widespread practice over many centuries. When they immigrated to other regions, Yemenis took the custom to their destinations, including Israel (Derfner, 1996).

Over time, Djibouti's indigenous residents embraced khat chewing as a practice of their Islamic faith and a culture of the people who spoke the language of the Prophet (Thompson and Adloff, 1968). Supplied by dhow from Yemen and after 1902 by train from the Harerge highlands, by the 1940s, chewing had become a widespread ritual practiced by a significant portion of the city's residents. Today, khat chewing in Djibouti is a ubiquitous practice involving the majority of the country's citizens. Every member of society, from the pauper on the streets to the president in

the palace, chews khat, regardless of economic and social background. Some chew to escape the miseries of a poverty-stricken life, others to keep them away from the searing sun, and still, others simply to indulge in a luxury (Fedarko, 2006).

This has prompted observers, such as Kevin Fedarko of Esquire magazine to describe Djibouti society as a narco-society, not because khat is a narcotic substance, but to denote the level of the extensiveness of its use. In this country, up to 56 percent of households have at least one user while as much as 80 percent of the adult population is said to chew the leaves regularly (Brown, 2009, Borelli, 2009).

In a country where unemployment reaches up to 60 percent (Kimball, 2007), chewers are willing to spend as much as a third and, in some cases, half of their household income on the leaves. And a casual interview on the streets of Djibouti as to why they spend money they do not have on khat elicits responses such as these: "Everything we do depends on our majesty; khat" and "khat is my brother. It takes care of everything." Some chewers, echoing Karl Marx's "opiate of the masses" dictum, invoke a more insidious conspiracy that, "if there was no khat, we'd have to think about more serious things, like criticizing the government" (Bengall, 2006).

Social and Economic Effects of Chewing Khat

Social Effects of Chewing Khat:

Khat chewing is an old practice in different parts of eastern and western Africa, the Middle East, and most Arabian Peninsula countries where the plant is widely disseminated (Al-Mugahed 2008). In Ethiopia; khat is widely used at social gatherings for stimulation and social recreation. Stimulation is usually attained by chewing the young buds and tender leaves privately or in small social gatherings (Cochrane, 2014). Increased appetite for social interaction, euphoria, excitement, and an increase in libido and levels of energy are some after-effects among khat-chewing individuals (Ageely and Kalix, 1988).

Among the positive social impacts of chewing khat, some chewers claim that khat gives them increased levels of energy; alertness; confidence; a sense of happiness; sensations of elation; enhanced imaginative ability and creativity; relaxation, and socialization and helps them to concentrate better or provides additional energy for physical labor (Dhaifalah et al, 2004). Khat is used both in a social and formal setting and its main function is stimulating sociability (Anderson et al, 2007).

Moreover, khat sessions are occasions for the exchange of information, and discussions on plans and decisions for communities in Yemen and central and eastern parts of Ethiopia. It is also culturally very significant that khat sessions are held during cultural functions like birth, circumcision, and marriage. People also use it as an enhancer to carry out their daily activities. Laborers chew khat during hard physical work, students when preparing for exams, and lorry drivers for long-distance travel to increase their level of concentration. Special khat sessions are also organized by clan elders and judges to settle disputes and court cases Lamina (2010).

Even though khat chewing is popular among the masses, there is substantial evidence that khat chewing harms social, mental, and physical well-being. Certain medical complications like adverse cardiovascular events, liver failure, stomach ulcers, depression and anxiety, psychosis, and impotence, among others have been found associated with khat chewers (Gashawa and

Getachew, 2014). Certain social behaviors like smoking, use of drugs, and alcohol have been associated with the khat-chewing populace (Tesfaye et al, 2008).

Given the majority of community members, chewers are less accepted and those people are trying to force them to cease chewing. This social exclusion contributes to family disruption. In family life, the expense of buying khat becomes the cause for conflict between the spouse with the husband as the husband spent more money on khat chewing. The chewers have also no adequate time and care for their families since he/she forgets his/her family (Amsalu et al, 2017).

The Economic Effect of Khat:

In the last decade, khat has emerged as one of the most important export cash crops in Ethiopia. It provides a means for rural livelihoods, a source of tax revenue, and is needed foreign currency for the government. The rate of increase in the revenue and foreign currency generated from khat is very high. During the 1990s, khat revenue averaged 1.7% of Ethiopia's GDP which was higher than the health expenditure of the country. Between 1998 and 2007 export production increased fourfold (from 5,670 to 22,667 tons) and the export value doubled Dessie (2013). Its contribution continued to grow and in 2014/15, khat accounted for 9 % of national exports with over 272 million US dollars (NBE, 2015).

The transporting, processing, packaging, and resale of khat have created employment opportunities across the region. According to a survey conducted by the Central Statistical Agency (2012), 2,409,701 households grew chat, covering 179,776 hectares of land in the budget year of 2011/2012. The above figure shows only the number of farmers. The number of people who make a living from khat would be highly inflated if all the agents in the value chain (wholesalers, transporters, and retailers) are also included. Unlike other crops, khat's market triumphs without any support from international development agencies or any form of government incentive or subsidy. Within Africa, khat use is spreading fast. Markets have developed in Eritrea, Sudan, Uganda, Rwanda, and South Africa.

It is believed that khat is now one of Ethiopia's major resources of internal tax revenue (Gebissa, 2008). Revenue officials cite that khat like other export commodities; fetches millions of dollars earning annually through customized trade deals. The majority of the khat trade is domestic hence the tax is collected at different regional and zonal levels. The domestic tax collection augments the total export tax collection revenue owing to a big export market (Feyisa and Aune, 2003).

Not only this but also employment opportunity created through the cultivation of khat is very high in that large numbers of people are involved in growing, harvesting, sorting, packing, transporting, loading, and unloading the commodity. The wood of the plant is commonly used for fuel and due to its resistance to termites is used in the construction of houses and fencing. It is also used for making rafters, handles of farm tools (hammers and chisels), and handles of household articles such as pots and pans, rolling pins, and to make forks, combs, spoons and for rulers (Anderson & Carrier, 2006; Anderson et al, 2006).

Beyond all, khat is the third largest export crop, next to coffee and oil seed. Hence, it plays a considerable role not only in the national economy, but also it is a major income source for millions of farming households, and traders who directly or indirectly depend on it (Aden et al, 2006; Bongard et al, 2011). Occupational groups such as motor vehicle drivers, and truck drivers,

who chew khat during long-distance driving, to keep awake, also use it under different conditions. More students chew khat to be vigilant, especially during the examination period. Khat is also used by special sections of the community: craftsmen and farmers use it to reduce fatigue and concurrently increase their work efficiency or performance (Muluneh, 2018).

In addition to this, people also use it as an enhancer to carry out their daily activities. Laborers chew chat during hard physical work, students when preparing for exams, and lorry drivers for long-distance travel to increase their level of concentration (Lamina, 2010).

However, Beckerleg (2010) and Branko (2008) argue that khat is an addictive substance with negative consequences. They believe that khat use makes users careless, less accountable, and irresponsible, thereby increasing social crime. In addition, they indicate that khat takes a significant share of the daily expenditure of regular users and hence diverts money away from productive activities.

It also leads to the loss of a job or a decrease in productivity even though this is common in long-time chewers and dependent groups. The long time they use for chewing at the expense of working time chewers may be fired from employment or lose their private job (Amsalu et al, 2017). More than this, Khat chewing may harm the economy through a loss in production as a result of laziness and absenteeism. Workers go to lunch and engage in Khat sessions, and do not return to work. A current estimate suggests that over 10 billion hours of work a year were lost as a result of the Khat habit (Muluneh, 2018). It may also lead to frequent misbehavior, poor economic, social and academic performance, and memory impairment among youths (Tsegaye et al, 2019).

The above empirical findings have revealed that khat was cited as part of the problem for the economies of Ethiopia, Yemen, Djibouti, and others, partly because, as statistics suggest, nearly every family spends one-third of its disposable income on khat consumption (Muluneh, 2018; Amsalu et al, 2017).

Prevalence of Khat Consumption

Khat chewing is a common practice in some Arab and other East African countries. Studies from Yemen; Djibouti and Uganda have shown similar trends. About 80% of Yemenis between the age of 15 and 30 chew khat daily. In Djibouti, 81.6% of men and 43.3% of women reported using khat at least once in their lifetime (Dessie, 2013).

In a study conducted on 10,000 Hargessa residents in Somaliland who were randomly selected for the purpose, 29.8% of the sample chewed khat. About 65% of the consumers also spend 7 hours per day chewing khat. Gender and age-wise, 95% are male and 75% are between the ages of 21 to 40 years (Sovoredo 2002 in Anderson et al, 2007).

In the Ethiopian highlands and along Kenya's coast, both regions where khat was not known until recently, the practice is spreading fast, especially among young people and some studies indicate that the peak age of khat chewing is between 18 to 44 years Klein et al (2012: 2 -3). "Globally, the demand for khat is growing but the global markets are driven by demand from diaspora populations, particularly from Somalia" (Klein et al, 2012). "An estimated 297 million khat chewing sessions are held every year which means that during any one day, 3.6% of Ethiopia's adult population chew khat, and the annual per capita annual consumption comes to 5.3 kg" (Dessie, 2013).

A nationwide demographic health survey conducted about the prevalence of khat chewing in Ethiopia among the total population in 2011 showed that the overall khat chewing at a national level was 15.3%, with significant regional variations. The lowest prevalence of 1.1% was reported in Tigray (the northern part of Ethiopia) and the highest prevalence of 53.2% was reported in Harari (the eastern part of Ethiopia). Compared to the capital city of Addis Ababa, much higher rates were observed in Oromiya, Southern Nations, Nationalities and People (SNNP), Gambella, Harari, and Dire Dawa regions with respectively 1.9, 1.6, 3.1, 5.2- and 3.5-times higher odds of chewing. As expected, females were 77% less likely to chew khat as compared to males. A multivariable analysis carried out in the same study also showed that Muslims were 23.8 times more likely to chew khat as compared to Orthodox Christians and adults in the age group 45–49 years were 3.6 times more likely to chew khat as compared to 15–19 years (Haile et al, 2015).

Contrary to the public perception that the poor and the unemployed consume khat more often, the study found that the middle and richest wealth quintiles chew 1.3 and 1.5 times more respectively. Rural residents had a 1.3 chance of chewing khat compared to urban residents and most of them are the farmers that grow the plant. Again contrary to public perception that the unemployed chew khat more often than any other group in society, it is the individuals who had occupations in sales, agriculture, the service sector, skilled and unskilled manual workers who chew chat 1.6, 1.3, 2.4, 1.7 and 2.3 more times respectively than the unemployed (Haile et al, 2015). Surprisingly consumption prevalence among educated Ethiopians is found to be much higher than the national average. In one particular research conducted on 450 people with academic qualifications of BSc; MSc and Ph.D. degrees, the prevalence rate was as high as 34% (Dessie, 2013). Other studies conducted on college students in Bahirdar and Jimma also showed a high prevalence rate of 27% and 30.6% respectively Gebissa (2008).

In conclusion, the survey identifies the highest wealth quintiles, older age group, rural residents, people with experience of child death, divorcees, males, regions of Oromiya, SNNP, Gambella, Harari, and Dire Dawa, and Muslims as groups with statistically significant association with khat chewing and it designated khat chewing as a public health concern (Haile et al, 2015).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Description of the Study Area

Dambi Dollo is the capital town of the Kelem Wollega zone, Oromia National Regional State of Ethiopia. The town is located 652 km west of Addis Ababa. It is bounded by Sayo Woreda in all directions. Being in the Sayyo woreda the town's main economic activities are based on trade, agricultural cash crops like coffee and khat, maize, and other staple crops. It has one public university and two colleges, two private university colleges, and an airport. Thus, workers of these institutions and students from different corners of the country are also dwelling in the town. Dambi Dollo town and its areas are well known in Khat production which is commonly known as "Abawari, Jaarro, mogoraa, Yemeni, Abagido, Abbaa abadir, and Garjeda khats. These types of Khat are known for their wide leaf structure and high stimulating capacity. The other type of Khat that is well-known in the study area is "Ayira khat" which is produced around Ayira woreda and shipped Dambi Dollo town market (DDTO, 2020).

Figure 1: Geographical location of the town
Source: Authors' computation using GIS

Research Design

The study used a cross-sectional descriptive research design. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches to data analysis were used by the researchers in analyzing the data.

Sources and Types of Data

Both qualitative and quantitative data were from primary sources. But before that, an exploratory survey was undertaken to gain familiarity with the study area and have firsthand information about the socio-economic impacts of khat in the study area.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

We have used a Snowball Sampling technique which is a non-probability (non-random) sampling method used when characteristics to be possessed by samples are rare and difficult to find. Thus, to identify youths who chew khat in the town an Exponential snowball sampling technique was employed. This technique is consistent because, in our study area, obtaining a sample study of khat chewers is difficult since they hide and are not willing to be exposed (Crossman and Ashley, 2020). Concerning the level of accuracy, a confidence level of 95% as suggested by Kothari (2005), means that there are 95 chances in 100 (0.95 in 1) that the sample results represent the true condition of the population within a specified precision range against 5 chances in 100 (or .05 in 1) that it does not.

To calculate the sample size, n , is needed using the estimated population proportion, p , where z is the z -value yielding the desired degree of confidence, p is an estimate of the population proportion, and e is the absolute size of the error in estimating p that the researcher is willing to permit, the following is appropriate. If no previous estimate of p is available, using $p = 0.5$ in the sample size formula will yield the maximum size n required for any given e and z (Abdi, 2012).

$$n = \frac{z^2(1-p)(p)}{e^2} = \frac{1.96^2(1-0.5)(0.5)}{0.05^2} \cong 384$$

Where, n =sample size, z = z value at 95%=1.96,

e =size of error in estimating =0.05, and p =0.5

Therefore, a total sample size of 414 respondents will be selected.

Methods of Data Collection

Before using a semi-structured interview schedule, pre-testing was done among non-sampled respondents with matching characteristics. Afterward, qualitative data was collected through focus group discussion, key informant interviews, In-depth interviews, and personal observation; and a five-point Like-heart scale was used to measure the affective state of chewers. In addition, secondary data was collected from reports and published materials. Data related to social and economic affairs will be collected from different stakeholders like Kebele administrators, the Ministry of Finance and Ministry of agriculture, and the Market Development and Trade Office of the Zone and the town.

Methods of Data Analysis

STATA version 13 was used to analyze the quantitative and qualitative data. STATA ran to analyze descriptive statistics such as frequencies and generate tabulated reports, and charts, and identify factors influencing for chewing or non-chewing behavior of the respondents accordingly. Qualitative data gained from FGDs, and interviews were described, analyzed, and interpreted on spot during data collection to avoid missing relevant information.

Ethical Consideration

During data collection, we will inform the purpose of the study, and all information obtained from the respondents was used only for solving society's problems and kept confidential. We have followed the research guidelines, rules, and regulations of Dambi Dollo University as well as the norms and customs of the society.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Demographic Characteristics

Of the total 384 questionnaires distributed to be filled during the survey period, about 384 (100%) were filled and collected. The demographic characteristics of the respondents like education level, marital status, job status, religion, birthplace, and having a child or not are presented in this section. This study was focused on youths aged from 19 years old to 35 years old. The results revealed that the ages of respondents ranged from 19 to 35 years with a mean of 27 years. This result is consistent with many empirical works of literature related to the impacts of chewing khat on youths (Table 1).

Gender of the Respondents:

According to the figure, the following majority of youths chewing khat in Dambi Dollo town in 2022 were male (87%) and the remaining were females (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Gender of the Respondents
Source: Authors' calculation from the survey, 2022

Religion of the Respondents:

The results revealed that 48% of chewers among youths in the town were reported as Christians tracked by Muslims (46%), wakefana(5%), and others (1%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Percentage Distribution of Chewers by their religion
Source: own computation from the survey, 2022

According to the above figure 2, chewing behavior and being Christian religion are highly related to chewing behavior, keeping other things constant. However, this finding is not consistent with most of the other findings reported: "Khat chewing is reported to be mostly associated with the Muslim religion." Studies showed that in areas where many followers live side by side, the khat chewing percentage is higher among Muslims than among other beliefs. Gelaw and Haile-Amlak

(2004) as cited in (Getahun, 2017) reported that among a sample of Ethiopian staff at Jimma University, Muslim Khat chewers comprised of higher percentage (49%) than chewers from other different faith backgrounds. Ayana et al. (2002) reported significant associations between being a Muslim and chewing Khat. The result is contradicted may be because of the high proportion of Christian religion followers in our study area, Dambi Dollo town than the study areas of the above-mentioned literature. Thus, not surprisingly, figure two of the above revealed that Christian khat chewers include of higher percentage (48%) than others.

Educational Level of the Respondents:

The results from table 1 below showed that about 11% of the sample respondents were illiterate, 9% were grades 1-8, 23%, were grades 9-12, and the remaining 56% attended college/university level (Figure 3). According to this figure, the majority of youths chewing khat in the town were those who were graduates of college or university and above. This may reveal that as the educational level increases, keeping other things constant, the percentage of chewers also increased. This finding may be consistent with the fact that as educational level increases the number of graduates of college and university also increases and if there are no employment opportunities that absorb them they will be unemployed. And a majority of youths invited to fill out the questionnaires for this study reported that they use khat for recreation because of a lack of a job to do (Figure 7).

Figure 3: Percentage distribution of chewers by their educational level

Source: Authors' computation from the survey, 2022

Marital Status of the Respondents:

About 57% of the sample respondents were single, about 39% were married, 3% were divorced and the remaining 1%, were widowed (Table 1).

Figure 4: Percentage of respondent’s distribution by their marital status
Source: Authors' computation from the survey, 2022

The above figure shows that the majority of khat users in Dambi Dollo town were single youths. This finding is consistent with that of

"How Do you Start Chewing?":

This question was presented to respondents in the questionnaire. The majority of them have reported that they started chewing khat of peer pressure(59%), as an adventure(20%), at school for reading, and the remaining(2%) by family as a culture.

Figure 5: Percentage distribution of respondents by how they started chewing khat
Source: Authors' computation from a survey, 2022

The Economic Impacts of Chewing Khat Among Youths of Dambi Dollo Town.

According to figure 6 below, the majority of the chewers were earning above 5000 ETB, followed by 3001 ETB – 5000 ETB, below 1500 ETB, and between 1501 ETB and 3000 ETB. Which accounts for 32%, 25%, 26%, and 17% respectively. This implies that the average monthly income of youth khat chewers in the town was about 3500 ETB (Table 2). However, the monthly average expenditure on the leaf of khat for one individual young chewer in the town was estimated as of about 2000 ETB, keeping other things remain constant.

Out of the total respondents of our study, the majority of them (37%) spent 2001 ETB to 3000 ETB, 29% of them spent 1001 birr to 2000, 23% of them spent below 1000 birr and the remaining 11% spent above 3000 birrs per month on khat consumption only. This consumption expenditure was calculated excluding the additional expenditures on substances taken during and after khat use. Since personal saving is the income left over after tax and consumption,

Respondent 5: "Galiin an ji'aan argadhu dhaabbataa waan ta'eef baasiin an caatiif baasu diinagdee koo irratti dhiibbaa guddaa qaba" Translated as "The khat expenditure has a high negative effect on my economy since my income earning is fixed."

The additional khat consumption expenditure decreases the probability and amount of personal savings. Not only personal savings but also the high amount of expenditure on khat consumption may decrease the amount of income allocated for other important personal consumptions including basic needs, keeping other things constant.

According to our findings, the majority of khat users were male self-employed youths who chew khat almost daily to be more productive. However, the daily spending on khat may decrease the probability of expanding their business and their saving too. Khat chewing also affects the economy of the chewers since it leads to loss of working hours or absenteeism from work as well as utilization of money to buy the Khat rather than expensing for buying nutritious foods and care of household members. According to (Bengali, 2006), even the unemployed chewers spend more than 60% of their income on khat consumption.

The above finding is also consistent with other empirical findings that support khat takes a significant share of regular users' budgets. It revealed that there are cases where regular users secure their daily consumption of khat at the expense of vital needs, indicating dependence. Moreover, family life is damaged because of neglect, dissipation of family income, and inappropriate behavior (Jemal Abafita, Badas Wolteji Chala, Ksahun Eba, Kyung Kim, and Chang-Soo Kim, 2015).

Respondent₁ "Caatii walitti fufinsaan qaamuun koo qusannaa koo hir'isee, diinagdeen koo akka kufu godheera". This statement is translated as "My income saving was decreased and this negatively affected my economy because of frequently chewing."

The economic impact of chewing khat may depend on the frequency of chewing per week and the purpose of chewing too. The monthly expenditure on khat consumption and the frequency of khat sessions per week are highly associated with each other. Users who consume daily spent more of their income on khat consumption. This shows that chewing khat frequently increases the total expenditure on khat consumption per month which in turn may decrease the youth's income left for other important consumption and saving.

Moreover, figures 5 and 6 reveal that the gap between average monthly income and monthly consumption expenditure on khat only is small. Keeping other things constant, individuals allocate their income for food, monthly rental fees, children's tuition fees, tuition fees, and other important activities. Accordingly, frequent khat session per week, using additional substances with khat, chewing outside of the home, and chewing for recreation increases the expenses of young chewers which in turn decrease their ability to meet their present need and future consumption or welfare.

The above finding is consistent with that of (Zerihun Girma Gudata, Logan Cochrane, and Gutema Imana, 2019) who found that khat consumption habit affects the economy of consumer households by negatively influencing their income usage and time management. The habit of khat consumption is also negatively associated particularly with the work culture of government employees, as they leave for lunch break early and come back to work late.

Respondent 4: " Miidhaan diinagdee caatii qama'uun fidu galii namaa xiqqeessuu, yeroo gubuudhaan akka namni yeroo hojii isaa hin fayyadamne godha." Translated as: "wastage of working time, and decreasing income are the negative effects of chewing khat."

The above response revealed that khat chewing affects the economy of the chewers since it leads to loss of working hours or absenteeism from work as well as utilization of money to buy the Khat rather than spending on buying nutritious foods and care of household members. This is indirectly linked to absenteeism and unemployment which in turn leads to a reduction in overall economic activity.

Respondent 2: " Miidhaan Caatiin fidu inni guddaan yeroo waan ittin bitanii qaaman dhaban, miira mukaa'uu fi gommuu waan fiduuf hojii irratti dhiibbaa fida." Translated as "The greatest negative effect of chewing khat are deep depression and lack of motivation for work when not chewed."

This may reveal that youths became dependent on the leaf to accomplish their economic activities productively. Consequently, working hours and possibly productivity could be decreased when khat is not used, because of reduced motivation.

Figure 6: percentage distribution of Respondents by their average monthly expenditure on khat consumption

Figure 7: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by their average monthly income
 Source: Authors' computation from the survey, 2022

Figure 8: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by their job status
 Source: Authors' calculation from the survey, 2022

Out of the total youths who were absent from their job at least two times per week due to khat sessions, 45% of them were those who chew for recreation purposes, 29 % of them were those who chew to be active in their job and the remaining 26% of them were those who chew to socialize with others (Table 1).

Table 1: The purpose of chewing khat vs Absent from work/job or not Absenteeism from work/job

why chewing khat	Absenteeism from work/job		
	No	Yes	Total
To Worship	0	1	1
To Socialize with others	55	56	111
To be more active in my job	67	62	129
For recreation	49	94	143
Total	171	213	384

According to figure 8 above out of the total sampled respondent's majority (36%) of them were self-employed youths. According to table 1 above, out of the total self-employed khat chewers in Dambi Dollo town 59% consume khat daily to be more active in their jobs.

However, according to Respondent 9 below, moderate khat chewing may help to accomplish activities efficiently and confidently.

Respondent 9: "Yeroo tokko tokko caatii fayyadamuun hojii ofii saffisaan akka raawwataniif nama gargaara akkasumas miira soda balleessuun ofitti amanamummaan akka hojjetan nama gargaara" Translated as "Moderate Khat chewing helps to accomplish the job efficiently and confidently."

This finding is consistent with that of (Beyehu and Garoma Desa, 2020), in which users reported that moderate khat use results in increased energy level and alertness, improves self-esteem, creates a sensation of joy, enhances the imaginative ability and the capacity to associate ideas and improves the ability to communicate, improves performance and increases work output, owing to the stimulant and fatigue postponing effect.

This shows that the economic effect of chewing khat depends on the nature of the jobs youths are employed on. This finding is also consistent with that of (Rashid A. Omar, Mutundu K. Kennedy, and LeviN.Mbugua, 2019) who found that the highest percentage of Khat consumers had at least secondary education and were self-employed.

The Social Impacts of Chewing Khat Among Youths in Dambi Dollo Town

The result from the study indicated that Khat chewing was fairly high with statistically significant associations with sex, religion, Marital status, and income. The respondents have also reported, spending a significant amount of money and time on Khat chewing and facing problems of not participating in social relationships with society,

Respondent 6: " Namoota caatii qama'an qofaa waliin hariiroon akka uumamu gochuun hawwasa biroo irraa adda nama qooda" Translated as "It made you create solo-relationship with chewers excluding you from other parts of the society"

The above response revealed that frequently chewing khat results in exclusion from society and hinders participation in different social celebrities and problems which in turn results in the exclusion of the family of chewers.

Respondent 8: "Caatii qama'uun akka jireenya hawwaasuma kannen akka cidhaa, mana gaddaa fi kannen kana fakkaatan irratti hin hirmaanne nama godha." Translated as "Chewing khat restricts you from participating in social celebrities and problems like marriage, funerals, etc."

According to the response of Respondent 8, frequent khat users are restricted from neighbors' or kin's marriage, funeral, and others because khat session consumes more time and affects carelessness.

Moreover, the time-consuming nature of khat sessions also negatively affects the time allotted for families, children, couples, and friends too. According to figure 9 below, the majority of youths chew outside of the home which may incur additional expenses and additional substance intake too. This also reveals that families were not getting time with the users which may decrease the positive spirit and close relationship between or among them.

Not only this it was also revealed that many men were said to use a portion of the family budget on khat at the expense of vital needs. Family life is harmed as a result of neglect; the indulgence of family income is hence the main factor in family arguments which may result in divorce. This finding is consistent with the findings of (Mohamed, Jibril, and Ibrahim, Yusuf, 2012) which posited that the frustrations of the chewer as a result of the little sleep he had, coupled with the tensions that resulted from the arguments on his late coming the previous night, lead to aggressions on the side of the chewer. As one can imagine, with the prolonged tension between the couples, the harmony in the family might be affected hence dysfunctions in the family.

Figure 9: The percentage distribution of chewers by where they chew
Source: Authors computation from the survey, 2022

Moreover, chewing khat may have a negative social impact on the future as children imitate the youths of their neighbors (Respondent 10).

Respondent 10: "Jjoolotni ol-adeemoon namoota dargaessa ilaalanii amala caatii qama'uu irraa baruu waan danda'aniif hawwaasummaa irratti dhiibba gadhee qaba." Translated as "It has a negative social effect because children may imitate youths of their neighbors through which they will be addicted to it."

Contrary to the above findings, respondents reported that they would be non-violent and positive thinkers when chewing than not chewing. This may help society through the reduction of conflicts and living with diversity.

Respondent 7: "Faayidaan caatii qama'uu inni guddaan hawwasa keessa jiraadhu keessatti ilaalcha gaarii akkan qabaadhuu fi walitti bujinsaa namoota waliin akka hir'isuuf na gargaarera." Translated as "Chewing khat has benefited me to have positive thinking and in reduction of getting in conflicts with others."

According to the above finding, the negative social of chewing is more outweigh its positive as reported by the sampled respondents and related works of literature.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The habit of chewing Khat leaves (*Catha edulis* Forsk) is widespread in certain areas of East Africa including Ethiopia. This study was focused on assessments and analysis of the economic and social impacts of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town using primary data collected through structured questionnaires with an interview from 384 total sampled respondents by snowball sampling technique. We have used a cross-sectional descriptive to design our study and STATA version 13 was employed to run descriptive statistics, figures, charts, graphs, and other important statistics.

The descriptive statistics showed that out of the total youths chewing khat in the town, during the survey, 33% of them have a child and the rest have not, during the month of the survey. The majority of the respondents were Christian by religion (48%), single (57%), and Self-employed (36%). The majority of youths chewing khat in Dambi Dollo town in 2022 were single males, Christian, college graduates and above, and who were born in rural, on average.

In this study, the effects of Khat chewing were fairly high with statistically significant associations with sex, age, religion, social factor, and income. The reports also indicated that youths were spending a significant amount of money and time on Khat chewing and faced economic and social problems they attributed to their habit.

Accordingly, we have investigated that frequent khat chewing, chewing outside of the home, using additional substances, using khat for recreation, and being absent from the job for khat sessions were factors that are associated with the negative economic effect of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town and their families. Related to this, low saving culture, debt, decreased families budget, dependency, wastage of time and unemployment are the negative impacts of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town. Where moderate consumption of khat for work purposes which results in the accomplishment of activities efficiently and confidently was identified as a major positive economic impact of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town.

In addition, social exclusion, reduced family time and divorce were major identified negative social effects of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town.

Recommendations

Based on the finding made in the previous chapter, the negative economic and social impacts of chewing khat among youths in Dambi Dollo town outweighs its positive impact. Therefore, a policy intervention through strategy, plans, and programs is mandatory and recommended to have productive youths. In the effort to control the increasing use of Khat among youth in Dambi Dollo town the government should work toward the following forwarded options

Creating awareness of the negative consequences of frequent khat chewing on a social, economic, and financial situation to youth.

Create more opportunities for employment that will engage employees for most of their day time, from morning to evening. This could be achieved through government initiatives, NGOs, or the private sector, among others.

Devising Strategic intervention on the reduction of khat consumption by youth which may include investment in urban youths through training, sport, public lecture, and learning. This may also include building or establishing public libraries, youth sports centers, and rehabilitation centers, particularly for lifetime addicted youths in the town.

Preparing public lectures on the negative economic and social impacts of frequent khat consumption khat for youths.

Host intra- and inter-community competitions packaged with economic incentives (e.g., education, volunteer work, football, martial art, and athletics, among others). maybe three times per year. This may create opportunities for the youths so that they could be busy running and preparing for it than chewing khat as an option to pass time.

REFERENCE

- Adane, T., Worku, W., Azanaw, J., & Yohannes, L. (2021). Khat Chewing Practice and Associated Factors among Medical Students in Gondar Town, Ethiopia, 2019. *Substance Abuse: Research and Treatment*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1178221821999079>
- Aden, A., Dimba, E. A. O., Ndolo, U. M., & Chindia, M. L. (2006). SOCIO-ECONOMIC EFFECTS OF KHAT CHEWING IN NORTHEASTERN KENYA.
- Awale, S. S. A., & Sheikh Ali, A. Y. (2018). Social and Economic Difficulties Caused by Khat Usage in Somalia. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 8(8). <https://doi.org/10.30845/ijhss.v8n8p21>
- Bekele Etana, M. (2018). Economic and Social Impacts of Khat (&i>Catha edulis Forsk&i>) Chewing Among Youth in Sebeta Town, Oromia Ethiopia. *Biomedical Statistics and Informatics*, 3(2), 29. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.bsi.20180302.14>
- Corkery, J. M., Schifano, F., Oyefeso, A., Ghodse, A. H., Tonia, T., Naidoo, V., & Button, J. (2011). Overview of literature and information on “khat-related” mortality: A call for recognition of the issue and further research. In *Annali dell’Istituto Superiore di Sanita* (Vol. 47, Issue 4, pp. 445–464). https://doi.org/10.4415/ANN_11_04_17
- Eticha, T., & Ali, D. (2016). Socio-Economic and Health Effects of Khat Chewing in Mekelle, Tigray Region, Ethiopia LEVELS AND EXPOSURE RISKS OF METALS IN LIPSTICKS IN MEKELLE, ETHIOPIA View project Socio-Economic and Health Effects of Khat Chewing in Mekelle, Tigray Region, Ethiopia (Issue 8). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312473011>

- Gebissa, E. (2010). Khat in the Horn of Africa: Historical perspectives and current trends. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 132(3), 607–614. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2010.01.063>
- Gudata, Z. G. (2020). Khat culture and economic wellbeing: Comparison of a chewer and non-chewer families in Harar city. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2020.1848501>
- Gudata, Z. G., Cochrane, L., & Imana, G. (2019). An assessment of khat consumption habit and its linkage to household economies and work culture: The case of Harar city. *PLoS ONE*, 14(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224606>
- Jemal, A., Badassa, W. C., Kasahun, E., Kyung Ryang, K., & Chang Soo, K. (2015). Khat use and its impact on academic performance: The case of Jimma University, Ethiopia. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 10(15), 2084–2095. <https://doi.org/10.5897/err2015.2351>
- Kandari, L. S., Yadav, H. R., Thakur, A. K., & Kandari, T. (2014). Chat (*Catha edulis*): a socio economic crop in Harar Region, Eastern Ethiopia. *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, 3(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-1801-3-579>
- Megerssa, B., Esayas, A., & Mohamed, A. (2014). Socio-Economic Impact of Khat in Mana District, Jimma Zone, South Western Ethiopia. In *Discourse Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences* www.resjournals.org/JAFS (Vol. 2, Issue 2). www.resjournals.org/JAFS
- Mulugeta, Y. (2013). Khat Chewing and Its Associated Factor among College Students in Bahir Dar Town, Ethiopia. *Science Journal of Public Health*, 1(5), 209. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.sjph.20130105.14>
- Rather, R. A., Berhanu, S., Abaynah, L., & Sultan, M. (2021). Prevalence of Khat (*Catha edulis*) Chewing and Its Determinants: A Respondent-Driven Survey from Hossana, Ethiopia. *Substance Abuse and Rehabilitation*, Volume 12, 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.2147/sar.s324711>
- Reda, A. A., Moges, A., Biadgilign, S., & Wondmagegn, B. Y. (2012). Prevalence and determinants of khat (*Catha edulis*) chewing among high school students in eastern ethiopia: A cross-sectional study. *PLoS ONE*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0033946>
- Rm, L., & Lamina S. (2013). THE CHEWING OF KHAT (*CATHA EDULIS*) IN THE HORN OF AFRICA AND ARABIAN PENINSULA: ECONOMIC OVERVIEW. In *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter)* (Vol. 3, Issue 2).
- Tamirat, M. (2020). A Historical Overview of Khat Production in Ethiopia. *Social Sciences*, 9(2), 49. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ss.20200902.12>
- Wabel, N. (2011). Psychopharmacological aspects of catha edulis (khat) and consequences of long term use: a review. *Journal of Mood Disorders*, 1(4), 187. <https://doi.org/10.5455/jmood.20111217095840>
- Bengali, S. (2006). Khat dominates male life in the tiny Muslim nation of Djibouti.
- Carrier N., and Klantsching. (2018). Quasilegality: Khat, cannabis and Africa's drug laws. *Third World*.
- Getahun, G. (2017). Prevalence of Khat Chewing and its Effects on Academic Performance among Wollega University Students.
- Jemal Abafita, Badas Wolteji Chala, Ksahun Eba, Kyung kim, and Chang-Soo Kim. (2015). Khat use and its impact on students academic performance: The case of Jimma University, Ethiopia. *Academic Journals*, 2084–2095.
- M, A., & Andualem. (2002). The Prevalence and socio-demographic characteristics of khat chewing in Jimma town. *Ethiopian journal of health*.
- Mohamed, Jibril and Ibrahim, Yusuf. (2012). Diverse effects of Khat on Somali families. *International Social work and social Problems*.

Rashid A. Omar, Mutundu K. Kennedy, and Levi N. Mbugua. (2019). Socioeconomic implication of khat consumption on the household economy. *International journal of research*, 137-147.

Zerihun Girma Gudata, Logan Cochrane, and Gutema Imana. (2019). An assessment of Khat Consumption habit and its linkage to household economies and work culture: the case of Harar City. *PLOS*.

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I. Questionnaires and Interviews

A. Basic background information and related

1. Address - Kebele-----
2. Age
 - A. 18-25 years
 - B. 26 -35 years
 - C. 36- 45 years
 - D. 46- 55 years
 - E. 56 years and above
3. Sex
 - A. Male
 - B. Female
4. Religion
 - A. Orthodox Christian
 - B. Muslim
 - C. Protestant
 - D. Catholic
 - E. Others
5. Educational status
 - A. Illiterate
 - B. 1 -8 grades complete
 - C. 9-12 grade complete
 - D. Diploma and above
6. Marital Status
 - A. Married
 - B. Single
 - C. Divorced
 - D. Widow
7. Do you have children?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
8. Do you have any other persons that are economically dependent on you?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
9. What do you do for a living?

- A. Daily worker
 - B. Employed at government/private institution
 - C. taxi/lorry driver
 - D. student at a higher institution
 - E. self-employed
 - F. unemployed
 - G. any other
10. Where was your childhood residence?
- A. Rural
 - B. woreda's town
 - C. Urban
 - D. any other _____
11. Where is your most frequent khat session?
- A. Home
 - B. Friends' home
 - C. Special room for khat chewing
 - D. at work place with friends outside
 - E. Road side/under shade/
 - F. Specify if other _____
12. How did you start chewing?
- A. It is a family tradition
 - B. Through friends
 - C. At college/school, to help me in my studies
 - D. As an adventure
 - E. Please specify if any other _____
13. Do you believe that chewing khat helps you to do more of your jobs?
- A. Yes
 - B. No
14. If your answer for question number 13 is yes, how it helps you?
- _____
- _____
- _____
- _____
15. How often do you consume khat?
- A. Daily
 - B. one times a week
 - C. two times a week
 - D. At weekends
 - E. Specify if other _____
16. How do you obtain khat?
- A. Direct buying from sellers
 - B. I give money to another person to buy it
 - C. I take Khat from another person
 - D. An elder person gives me Khat
 - E. Specify if other _____
17. Do you think obtaining khat is easy for you?
- A. Yes

- B. Yes, to some extent
 - C. No
18. On average how long do you stay normally without consuming khat? If you do not find khat for a various reason
- A. a day
 - B. two days
 - C. three days
 - D. four days
 - E. a week
 - F. a month and above
19. What happens if you do not consume khat as per your schedule?
- A. Cannot work well
 - B. not treat others well
 - C. not happy
 - D. isolates me to fight with others
 - E. Drinking alcohol
 - F. If other specify it_____
20. Why do you consume khat? (you can select more than two answers)
- A. To pray (for worship)
 - B. to have better social interaction
 - C. to get a good mood for reading
 - D. to get energy for work
 - E. for entertainment
 - F. If others specify_____
21. Who consumes khat in your family including you?
- A. Father
 - B. mother and father
 - C. other relatives
 - D. the whole family
 - E. Elder Brother/Sister
 - F. younger Brother/Sister
 - G. None of them

B. The use of khat and its socioeconomic effects (income, use of time, and productivity)

1. What is your monthly income/what was your monthly income when you were chewing khat?
- A. Less than 1,500 birr
 - B. 1,501 - 3000 birr
 - C. 3001- 5000 birr
 - D. more than 5,000
 - E. If other Specify_____
2. How much money do you spend/did you use to spend/for a single khat chewing session?
- A. Less than 100-birr
 - B. 100 - 200 birr
 - C. 200- 300 birr
 - D. more than 300 birr
 - E. If other Specify_____
3. In your experience, how long does/did/ one khat chewing session take?

- A. Less than 30 minutes
 - B. 31 – 60 minutes
 - C. 1-2 hours
 - D. 2- 3 hours
 - E. More than 3 hours
4. What is /was/ the most common time that you chew khat?
 - A. In the morning
 - B. In the afternoon
 - C. In the evening
 - D. During the night
 5. Have /Did/ you ever been absent from your working place to chew khat?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 6. If your response to Q5. is "Yes", how often does/did/ this happen?
 - A. 2-3 times a week
 - B. 4 to 6 times a week
 - C. Once in week
 - D. Once in two weeks
 - E. Once a month
 - F. very rarely
 7. Have /Did / you ever been late to work because of khat chewing?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 8. If yes, how often does /did/ this happen?
 - A. 2-3 times a week
 - B. 4 to 6 times a week
 - C. Once a week
 - D. Once in two weeks
 - E. Once a month
 - F. very rarely
 9. Have / Did / you ever left /leave/ your job early to chew khat?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 10. If your response to Q. 9 is "Yes", how often does /did/ this happen?
 - A. 2-3 times a week
 - B. 4 to 6 times a week
 - C. Once a week
 - D. Once in two weeks
 - E. Once a month
 - F. very rarely
 11. Have / Did/ you ever sacrificed /sacrifice/ your family time to chew khat?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 12. If your response to Q. 11 is "Yes", how often does/did/ this happen?
 - A. 2-3 times a week
 - B. 4 to 6 times a week
 - C. Once in a week
 - D. Once in two weeks

- E. Once in a month
 - F. very rarely
13. In your opinion, is /was/ chewing khat helping you to be more effective /productive/ in your job/activity, OR is /was/ it making you less effective?
 - A. It is//was /making me more effective.
 - B. It is/was/ making me less effective.
 - C. If other Specify_____
 14. If your response to Q.13 is Choice A, how does/did/ it make you effective?
 - A. It helps /helped/ me to be more focused
 - B. It makes /made/ me more active/alert.
 - C. It gives /gave/ me more energy
 - D. It makes /made /me more imaginative
 - E. Please specify any other_____
 15. If your response to Q.13 is Choice B, how does /did / it make you less effective?
 - A. It makes/made/me less focused
 - B. It makes/made / me less active/alert.
 - C. It makes/made / me physically weak
 - D. It makes/made / me disillusioned
 - E. Please specify any other
 16. Have /Did / you ever faced /faced / financial shortage to buy khat?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 17. If your response to Q 16. is "Yes", what did you do to get the money?
 - A. I borrowed money
 - B. I bought Khat on credit
 - C. I did nothing
 - D. Specify if any_____
 18. Do you believe studying under the influence of khat has helped you get better results in exams?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 19. Do/Did you use any other substances while consuming khat ?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 20. If your response to Question no.19 is "Yes", what substance do/did you use?
 - A. Cigarettes
 - B. Alcohol
 - C. Soft drinks
 - D. Sugar
 - E. Water
 - F. Coffee/tea
 - G. Milk
 - H. Hard drugs
 - I. Please specify if any other _____
 21. Why do/did you use the other substances while chewing khat?
 - A. To get more excitement
 - B. To make chewing easier
 - C. For a better taste

- D. To reduce the toxic effect
- E. Please specify if any other _____
- 22. If your response to Question Number 19 is "Cigarettes", did you develop the habit of smoking cigarettes after you start chewing khat ?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- 23. If your response to Question number 19 is "Alcohol", did you develop the habit of drinking alcohol after you start chewing khat ?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- 24. If your response to Question number 19 is "Hard drugs", did you develop the habit of using hard drugs after you start chewing khat ?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- 25. At the end of the chewing session, what do/did you do to break the mirqana (as "Cabsii") (the highest level of the euphoric effect)?
 - A. I do/did not do anything
 - B. I drink/used to drink/ alcohol
 - C. I smoke/used to smoke /cigarettes
 - D. I use/used/ hard drugs
 - E. I drink/ used to drink/ milk
 - F. Please specify any other _____

26. What do you think is/are the social disadvantages of chewing khat?

27. What do you think is/are the social advantages of chewing khat?

28. What do you think is/are the economic advantages of chewing khat?

28. What do you think is/are the economic disadvantages of chewing khat?

Thank you for your cooperation!!

II. Selected Responses from the sampled Respondents

Respondents were invited to respond to the question **"What do you think are/are the economic disadvantages of chewing khat?"** Accordingly, they have written the following statements in the Oromo language and translated them into English.

Respondent 1: "Caatii walitti fufinsaan qaamuun koo qusannaa koo hir'isee, diinagdeen koo akka kufu godheera". This statement is translated as "My income saving was decreased and this negatively affected my economy because of frequently chewing."

Respondent 2: " Miidhaan Caatiin fidu inni guddaan yeroo waan ittin bitanii qaaman dhaban, miira mukaa'uu fi gommuu waan fiduuf hojii irratti dhiibbaa fida." Translated as "The greatest negative effect of chewing khat are deep depression and lack of motivation for work when not chewed."

Respondent 3: " Yeroo qama'an nama of wallaalchisee abdii sobaa namatti horee, yeroo booddee dhibaa'aa nama godha." Translated as: "It made you lazy and unproductive in the long run through giving fake hope during chewing session"

Respondent 4: "Miidhaan diinagdee caatii qama'uun fidu galii namaa xiqqeessuu, yeroo gubuudhaan akka namni yeroo hojii isaa hin fayyadamne godha." Translated as: "wastage of working time, and decreasing income are the negative effects of chewing khat."

Respondent 5: "Galiin an ji'aan argadhu dhaabbataa waan ta'eef baasiin an caatiif baasu diinagdee koo irratti dhiibbaa guddaa qaba" Translated as "The khat expenditure has a high negative effect on my economy since my income earning is fixed."

Respondent 6: " Namoota caatii qama'an qofaa waliin hariiroon akka uumamu gochuun hawwasa biroo irraa adda nama qooda" Translated as "It made you create solo-relationship with chewers excluding you from other parts of the society"

Respondent 7: "Faayidaacaatii qama'uu inni guddaan hawwasa keessa jiraadhu keessatti ilaalcha gaarii akkan qabaadhuu fi walitti bu'insa namoota waliin akka hir'isuuf na gargaarera." Translated as "Chewing khat has benefited me to have positive thinking and in reduction of getting in conflicts with others."

Respondent 8: "Caatii qama'uun akka jireenya hawwaasuma kannen akka cidhaa, mana gaddaa fi kannen kana fakkaatan irratti hin hirmaanne nama godha." Translated as "Chewing khat restricts you from participating in social celebrities and problems like marriage, funerals, etc."

Respondent 9: "Hojii ofii saffisaan akka raawwataniif nama gargaara akkasumas miira soda balleessuun ofitti amanamummaan akka hojjetan nama gargaara" Translated as "Chewing khat helps to accomplish the job efficiently and confidently."

Respondent 10: "Ijoollotni ol-adeemoon namoota dargaessa ilaalanii amala caatii gama'uu irraa baruu waan danda'aniif hawwaasummaa irratti dhiibba gadhee qaba." Translated as "It has a negative social effect because children may imitate youths of their neighbors through which they will be addicted to it."

III. STATA DESCRIPTIVE OUTPUT RESULTS

Table 1. Summary statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Gender	384	0.869792	0.336972	0	1
Religion	384	1.598958	0.650847	1	4
Education level	384	3.247396	1.023863	1	4
Marital Status	384	1.666667	0.590024	1	4
Do you a Have child?	384	0.328125	0.470143	0	1
Job-status	383	1.989556	0.799146	1	3
Birth place	384	0.585938	0.493202	0	1
Where do you usually chew khat?	384	0.627604	0.484074	0	1
How do you start chewing Khat?	384	2.565104	0.830823	1	4
Do you thin Chewing khat has an advantage?	384	0.505208	0.500625	0	1
What is your average chewing time per?	384	2.807292	1.200239	1	4
Why do you chew khat?	384	3.078125	0.817013	1	4
Monthly Income	384	2.638021	1.179331	1	4
Monthly expense of Expense of khat consumption	384	2.364583	0.962696	1	4
Absent from work cause of chewing khat?	384	0.554688	0.497649	0	1
Age	384	27.20313	3.450567	19	35

The Syzygy of the Operations and Drawbacks of Pos (Point of Sale) in Nigeria as a Financial Inclusion Product.

Odebola Taiwo James

Abstract:

This work is pivotal on the operations and downsides of the Point of Sale (POS) operators cum operations in Nigeria, a fusion of the prevalent advantages and the disadvantages of the business. It is an article reviewing the merits of their operations, the issues faced by merchants and their numerous customers, more importantly, are the shortfalls confronting the operators in relation to imminent issues attendant in their operations on occasions when there is bank network problem. However, this work takes cue from existing online articles most of which are recent to buttress and justify the positions and submissions on which the article is pivoted. The article sits on the narrative and fact that POS, as e-payment channel engenders financial inclusion and takes banking to the underserved areas as the increasing importance of financial inclusion, a catalyst for economic growth and development is gaining momentum and has been embraced, hence POS as a digital payment platform and a financial inclusion product is significantly contributing to Nigerian economic and financial growth.

Keywords: Point of Sale, Banks Underserved Areas, Fintech, POS Operations in Nigeria, Agency Banking, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

POS terminal in Nigeria is presently an elixir providing financial solutions and digital payment stream to many individuals, households and areas in Nigeria, and it is basically operated by merchants as agency banking, particularly, serving areas and communities which are tagged as banks' underserved areas. Just like banks are mostly situated in commercially lucrative, secure areas or in proximity to markets and commercial hub or centres. Therefore, some areas which do not fall within these categories witness low or no presence of banks and their banking services or products which implies financial exclusion rather to inclusion. With the Federal government and CBN's eradication of illegal mounting and availability of ATM dispensing machines in the end of the first decade into the millennium made things worse. Although, it was to correct the anomalies observed in the allocation and location of some ATM machines at that time, as most bars, pubs, fuel or service stations were seen to be erecting ATM machines within and in front of their ventures. You could actually see the pattern was not in any regulatory or rational order. Hence, the reason why so many people pitched tent with the eradication of the illegally-erected ATM machines. Although, it increased the sufferings of the banks underserved areas and population, it was a constructive regulatory drive, that is the anomaly the present POS emergence operation has come to correct. Its importance is derived from the promise it holds as a tool for financial inclusion which is tantamount to economic development, particularly in the areas of poverty reduction, employment generation, wealth creation, improving welfare and general standard of living.(4) However, as much as the POS business is gaining popularity, not all POS machines are actively in operation, just as "the Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS) data shows that there are about 307,000 PoS machines in Nigeria as of March 2021, only 167,000 were active" Emeka Ejere (March 2022).(8)

PREMISES

In actual fact, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) introduced the PoS system and agent banking in 2013 to achieve financial inclusion and develop a cashless economy, (Kayode 2021).(18) The initiative of agency banking was first pioneered by the likes of PAGA payment solution as transaction agent and Fintech firm to facilitate payment and create financial solutions for the banks' underserved areas and the diaspora, PAGA laid the template and started on good pedestal by using or employing the services of registered shop-agents who were mainly dispersed within Lagos and some elite states. Paga payment solutions facilitated financial inclusion via agents, that is why according to Mojeed's article from Premium Times, the number of adults using financial service agents increased from about 4 million in 2018 to 26 million using agents in 2020.(1) Then, after the likes of PAGA financial platform that pioneered cash dispensing and transaction facilitation channel, the fuel stations were the ventures disposed to actually dispense cash via POS as they were the set of business entities with availability of POS machine and constant cash. This was followed by the emergence of POS operators both in shops and stalls, that is why Abubakar Idris in his article sub-titled, "In Nigeria, where there's a shop, there's a bank"(2) posited on the availability of digital payment agents which are prevalent in nooks and crannies of most cities in Nigeria as obtainable with PoS merchants. Advertently, POS machine came to prominence in Nigeria at the beginning of the second decade of the millennial.(14) The central bank and commercial banks are fully aware of the need for financial inclusion approach, the advantages of POS terminals and the fact that many areas are still underserved in terms of proximity to the banks and ATMs, hence, the central bank allowed commercial banks and Fintech firms to disburse POS terminals to willing customers who requested and do the required in the acquisition to help them in facilitating their businesses, for collection of money at points-of-sale or for use as agency banking, that was the initiative behind the fact as stated by NIBSS that "Customers go for PoS transactions,"(12) hence, the central bank of Nigeria is in full knowledge of the advantages and operations of POS terminals as financial inclusion intensive product.(24) Ever since then, 'Agency banking contributes significantly to banks' revenue growth driven by charges from electronic banking services'. Kayode (2021).(18)

The actual function of a POS machine varies as used which are for withdrawal(6) and savings, but one of the purposes in industrialized nations which is being intensified in Nigeria is to encourage cashless caveats and reduce the volume of money being carried by citizens,(5)(10) more so, the advantage to pay at onsite market with cards instead of cash as termed point-of-sale, but as Nigerian banks even use it for withdrawals that is why it is popularly used for agency banking and withdrawal purposes in Nigeria. That explains why, a random survey of several PoS points shows that cash withdrawals make up 90% of their daily transactions. David and Amaka (2021).(6) Advertently, these terminals presently still proffer payment and financial solutions to the pool of citizenry who are in need of fast and quick withdrawals or transactions especially when they cannot get to the banks or ATMs. From the Engineers forum article which stated that the Shared Agent Network Expansion Facilities (SANEF), a CBN initiative to oversee agency banking in Nigeria and promote financial inclusion, reportedly depicts an impressive year for the sector, data released showed an 859% surge in the volume of PoS transactions during the lockdown between March and April 2020.(9) The expectation remains that this POS terminals and agencies will continue to exist and mete out pecuniary solutions to the polity if they would abide by the financial or terminals' provider's regulatory terms and that of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). More inclusively, there exists numerous Fintech firms which are POS terminal providers and vendors which distribute the POS machines to agents that use it for transaction purposes for numerous end users. In an investigative article by David Agba and Amaka Ifeakandu from Lagos,

it was stated that "PoS transactions from 307,000 machines hit 15.67trn in 4 years in Nigeria".(6) The hope remains that they put necessary structures in place, but these merchants are more after profits from agents as they are for-profit organization. However, there are speculations that POS can be used for money laundering and fraudulent transactions, but this is an unfounded truth as every POS machine is traceable, registered and synced with an account or personalities which can be tracked or traced. This is one of the reasons for the article from Premium Times tagged "As POS agents reach millions in Nigeria, users lament fraud" by Mojeed.(1) Another article says 'fraudsters dent Nigeria's multi-billion-naira POS business and economy'. Harrison Edehe and Ijeoma Opara.(11)

More importantly, there is the need for further and constructive regulations for the POS vendors and agents to ensure strict adherence to stated terms as the not-so-long situation of the eradication of the non-traceable Bitcoin accounts in Nigeria is exemplary to the case of regulations which can affect any transaction or account which does not abide by the conditions of the Central Bank's monetary policy or Federal government's fiscal policy. However, as it is obtainable that Central Bank allow commercial banks to issue POS terminals to customers who requested and do the needful in the acquisition to help them in transacting businesses or for collections of money at points-of sale, hence, the Apex Bank is fully aware of the operations and merits of POS terminals. In actual fact, just like Lagos is the seat of all banks in Nigeria, having the highest number of bank branches than any other states, same applies that 'Lagos is the POS capital of Nigeria with about 70% of total transactions carried out in 2020', Tomiwa Onaleye,(22) howbeit, the upcoming and new generation POS terminal vendors or Fintech firms need to be regularized as POS gains popularity and momentum, to abide by the Central Bank's policies so as not to jeopardize or forfeit the purpose for POS terminals' operation in Nigeria, neither for business transactions or to be used as agency banking. According to Kayode's article from Techpoint platform, it says data from Nairametrics for Statista shows that the number of PoS payments increased significantly from 34 million in 2015 to 438.6 million in 2019.(18)(20) While Engineers forum, in its article submitted that in 2020, NIBSS recorded that Nigerian merchants and mobile money operators (MMOs) processed over 655 million PoS transactions valued at ₦4.7 trillion (\$13 billion), a 50% increase from 2019.(9)

POS terminals and agents are actually solutions to many peoples' pecuniary problems. Even people have now turned to them for loans asking them to lend them money to be paid at an interest synonymous to the charges for withdrawing such amount. To keep customers in the midst of many sellers, they tend to lend money to their viable customers that approach them, and they sometimes reduce the charges on deposits or withdrawals even as low as ₦50 to attract pool of customers(17). To further attract customers, they surcharge very little amount for sending high volume of money to encourage customers to come and save, deposit, send or transfer with them so that it will reduce the operators number of times and risks of going to banks to withdraw for disbursements to their flock of customers. One of the visible intervening functions of the point of sale during the lockdown, when all banks were closed due to global shutdown, and financial institutions could not deliver branch services to their pool of customers as submitted in the article "Coronavirus, Covid-19 and Its Centrifugal Effect."(16) It was the POS that came to the rescue of the citizenry. Although, ATM machines and other channels of transaction enabling platforms were supposedly working and customers were encouraged to approach these channels during the pandemic and shutdown, nevertheless, there were intermittent problems with their functionalities, but the POS operators were constantly coming to the rescue of the populace and their transactional needs. It was one of the periods that POS operation saw profit hikes.

One of the problems encountered by the operators is that most customers or people want to form some form of relationship with them, however, these relationships are targeted at a favorable future request from the operators in order to extend a short-term loan to them or that their transactions or card may be safe with them. One of the many reasons behind the relationship formation is to gain consideration for lesser deposit or withdrawing fees by having a cordial or amicable relationship with the POS operator, the customer-operator relationship is targeted at a moderate consideration for transaction fees while those without relationship, pay their normal service fees. The paradigm of this relationship creation is that it also exist in commercial banks where customers try to establish cordiality with attendant cashier or the branch manager, either to fast-track their transactions or prevent delayed processing of their requests during their visits to the branch, and for possible low interest rates on intended loans or for other proposals from over-the-counter teller attendants or the branch manager respectively. Generally, people are wise in their own caprices.

Inadvertently, network problem from the receiving or sending institutions can mar transactions and even sometimes cause controversies or discrepancies. As the confidence in POS terminals operation is just building, hence, people still dispute agents and terminal's decisions or actions unlike they do in the banks if same happened. According to Emeka Ejere (March 2022), his article titled 'Rising fraud threatens POS business' from The Hallmark news(8), as customers misconceive any unusual activity of the PoS operator as fraudulent act. There is also the problems of dispense error which pends transaction making the withdrawal or transfer on hold in transition, at this instance, the customers which are mostly the ones withdrawing from their accounts do not want to understand the issue-related case, howbeit, this issue of pending transaction problem which is always caused when either of the sending or receiving institution has network problem, particularly, network problem from the customer's transaction releasing financial institution or bank. This transaction issue mostly occurs as dispense error when customer is attempting withdrawal or put on hold in transit when customers are doing deposit or transfer. Unfortunately, this case breeds controversies, especially in withdrawal as the customer will not want to leave without collecting their money, the actual purpose for which he or she has visited POS at the initial instance. This sometimes degenerates into argument or issues as to whether customer will collect the value of the sum to be supposedly withdrawn, while the operator may want to maintain network problem from the customer's bank and therefore refer the customer to his or her bank for solution. This is one of the rationale behind the relationship formation, as the operator sometimes gives the total money on hold, which rarely happens though, to the customer if they are well known to them, as money intended for withdrawal or they share the risk depending on the relationship or the exigency of the intended withdrawn fund, the solution remains that the withdrawing client is referred to his or her bank or given the whole money or shared as to the fact of sharing the risk, while both parties go to their banks to find solutions to the pending withdrawal, by calling the customer care support desk of the issuing bank or by visiting the bank for complaints and dispute resolution. Although, there is immediate solution after lodging complaints either via contact channels of customer care centre or by visiting branch,(3) as they are the means stipulated for dispense error dispute resolutions in financial issue-related cases and customer management matters by commercial banks. Given for the resolution, mostly are 3-5 working days slated to complete or finalize resolution of the pending fund after which the default amount would be released and reimbursed to the customer's account, in rare cases are the customers referred back to the POS operators, its bank or financial institution as most of the resolutions are from the customers' releasing bank. Nevertheless, there are instances where the withheld fund is with the POS operators' financial institution.

Another disadvantage to the POS operators like many SMEs is they lack tools, especially the ones to detect counterfeit notes, where they may have to be employing their discretion and physical evaluation to detect fake currencies, unlike the commercial banks or financial houses who use counterfeit detecting instruments or machines to forestall shortages incurred by accepting such notes even unknowingly. So many banks put the caption that you can only do withdrawal above N100,000 at the counter, amounts below that are expected to use the ATM or POS, however, some people who are yet to trust POS operators still take their small transactions to banks. Another of the problems experienced by the operators newly, is the fact that their known customers approach them for credit and loans, which they find hard to drive when disbursed loans turn default. This is one of the moths eating and killing the plant of POS operators, even as strong as commercial banks are, unmonitored credit facilities can make them go bankrupt.

However, some POS machines with viable structures and notably with credible Fintech firms as vendors or from the commercial Banks have features that can enable them log or withdraw disputes just like that of the self-service all commercial banks' internet banking channel or phone application set up for logging issues or dispense errors for lasting solutions, although, this is already happening with some POS distributing agencies as they are merging their software's and transactional operations with that of the commercial banks, and this helps to resolve transaction or disputes faster, more so, this makes the dispute resolutions synonymous with the ATM dispense error from the commercial banks, but, the obtainable is evident in commercial banks as most dispense error are treated automatically, reversed instantly or within 24 hours, failing of which the customers may have to visit or call the branch for lasting solution. More importantly, there is the need for the Apex bank to sync the operations of the POS operators and that of the commercial banks as they are representatives for the underserved areas and customers. An example is that most of the PoS machines or terminals cannot open bank account except for those that are bank-issued machines. The Central Bank has to integrate their services and operations within the confines of the Apex bank's policies for financial inclusion. More resolutely, local POS merchants should be made or subjected to undergo strict registration to prevent fraudulent activities or money laundering be carried out by the operators or their supposed customers, the wallet operations of the POS terminals and accounts should be monitored and checked for necessary balance, as there should be a confirmed or credible personality or company registered to any POS terminal for proper monitoring, the new caveat now is that Bank Verification Number (BVN) is required to register and collect POS terminals, this is good for proper monitoring of transactions and personality behind a POS machine and its operations. Although, some of the POS terminals or operators have daily limits for cash withdrawal, but mostly not for transfers, while some have limit for same withdrawal and transfer. The more reason why according to Pulse NG,(19) members of the House of Representatives from Lagos called for the CBN to put stringent measures in place in regulating POS operations.(23)

Although, the commercial banks have reduced the activities of disbursing POS to agents, covertly now, the banks refer people to use the POS agents as it enhances their income, reduces the volume of visitors to bank for transactions. Now, banks are mainly opened to collect bulk and lump sum cash for deposit, give large sum of money as withdrawals to their customers or for customer care complaints and disputes resolutions, that is why an article posited according to data from the NIBSS portal that the adoption of PoS as a payment gateway has increased, while the use and acceptance of cheques has reduced drastically. The data further shows that Nigerians made use of PoS services 178.99 million times in the first two months of the year 2022, this is termed a 25.59% increase from 142.51 million times that it was used in the preceding year of

2021.(21) More so, just like the above from NIBSS, it was said that "Christmas Spending Pushes POS Transactions in Nigeria to All-Time High of N6.4 Trillion in 2021".(13)

Advertently, the POS business has succeeded in creating or generating jobs and engendered economic activities cum engagements for many people, and particularly, graduates who are looking for jobs or those jobless before the advent of the POS business emergence. The agency banking has been beneficial to many households and individuals who have delved into the industry as it has created employment or source of income from its involvement, and drafted many into workforce engagement. The emergence of the operation has actually helped with reducing unemployment and to certain extent induced workforce engagement. Abubakar Idris' article "A bank at every corner store" posited that agency banking is not only transforming, but enhancing Nigerian business sector.(2) Those who would have been jobless are now actively engaged with the POS operation in diverse locations either in a shop, temporarily-created stall or kiosks, even under umbrella-made improvise. These have caused engagement in workforce for those who otherwise would have been indigents or unemployed. According to Vanguard NG publication on September 20th, 2021,(25) which states that the process of starting a functional POS business is easy and can be completed within two weeks to one month, provided the intended operator meets the requirements by the host bank or Fintech vendor.

More significantly, low capital is needed to start the business unlike other businesses, the nascent POS business does not call for large sum of money for startup, a feasible minimum amount of N50,000 is termed adequate to initiate the business. The startup capital for the business is also minimized by the fact that you do not require a fancy shop to kick-start the business operation. Egun wrote on Business Day NG(7) about commencing a POS business, that the amount of money needed to initiate the business ranges from N80,000-100,000 inclusive of the money to get the POS machine. It is stipulated that this will also cover miscellanies in getting other logistics needed to kick-start the business. Egun in her article further says that an operator can consider a strategic location as a place where there are good number of people who will need to perform simple financial activities, while remote areas, markets, student environments, and places where banks and automated teller machines (ATMs) are of a distance from the people can be a promising or lucrative location to jumpstart the business.

However, as the confidence of the populace hitherto increases in the POS business, these engender patronage which in turn tunes up their sales, turnover and profit making as the merchants break-even and continue to stay in business, these attract others and new entrants into the agency banking industry. More so, as available presently, there is no barrier to entry into the business and competition is still healthy and fair, although, there is no existing structure or association regulating prices and activities except the available regulatory daily transaction limit from the commercial banks and the financial technology firms which basically are the POS main providers. All the above have cumulated into many entries into the ventures and industry creating enhanced participation in the economic activity and expanding employment opportunities. This backdrop is why the POS business is on the rise and the rationale behind the widespread acceptance and surge in its operations. The more reason why Channels Television in business News section stated that POS had the largest volume of transaction for the year 2021 at the tune of 2.3trillion exceeding the amount of transactions from checks and drafts, it was further stated that since Covid-19 emergence, the POS operations and transactions have skyrocketed, causing the volume to be enormous than its counterpart transactions from checks and over-the counter banking.(20)

9. EngineersForum. (July, 2021). The Activities of POS Agents in Nigeria. Techpoint, Entrepreneurship Section July 17, 2021. Retrieved online from <https://engineersforum.com.ng/2021/07/17/the-activities-of-pos-agents-in-nigeria/>
10. G. I Anyanwu and C. I. Anumaka. (2020). Point of Sale and Cashless Policy in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*. 20(2): 42-57, 2020; Article no. AJEBA.62040 ISSN: 2456-639X. Retrieved online from <https://www.journalaje.com/index.php/AJEBA/article/download/30323/56894>
11. Harrison Edeh and Ijeoma Opara. (March 2022). Fraudsters dent Nigeria's multi-billion-naira POS business. *Business and Economy*. March 10, 2022. Retrieved online from <https://www.icirnigeria.org/fraudsters-dent-nigerias-billion-naira-pos-business/#>
12. NIBSS. (March 2021). Customers go for PoS transactions. March 2021. NIBSS. Retrieved online from <https://nibss-plc.com.ng/news/42p2ht4m2gq2n3wzqxf8oyn6n3#>
13. NIBSS. (March 2022). Christmas Spending Pushes POS Transactions in Nigeria to All-Time High of N6.4 Trillion in 2021. NIBSS. Retrieved online from <https://nibss-plc.com.ng/news/4tn8jsmcdv5ns7r34sgos759dg>
14. NIBSS and Pos Transactions. (Feb, 2015). The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) introduced the Point of sale, 10 Feb 2015. Retrieved online from <https://allafrica.com/stories/201502101083.html>
15. Nwachukwu Kingsley, Agim Levi Okechukwu, Gyang Dalyop Francis, Monulu Racheal Uju. (2019). Agency Banking, Mobile Money Operations and Financial Inclusion in Jos Town, Nigeria. *Journal of Mgt. Science & Entrepreneurship*. December 2019. JMSE 2019 Vol. 17 No. 7. Retrieved online from https://www.hummingbirdpubng.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/HUJMSE_44-65.pdf
16. Odebola Taiwo James. (2020). Coronavirus, Covid-19 and Its Centrifugal Effect. *Advanced Research Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology (ARJPHE)* ISSN 5167-4231 Vol. 5(1), pp. 065-070, February, 2020. *Advanced Scholars Journals*. Retrieved online from <https://advancedscholarsjournals.org/full-articles/coronavirus-covid-19-and-its-centrifugal-effects.pdf?view=download>
17. Oladeinde Olawoyin. (Dec. 2019). Stop compelling Nigerians to pay N50 on POS transaction, CBN tells business owners. By Oladeinde Olawoyin, on December 24, 2019. Retrieved online from <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/business/369677-stop-compelling-nigerians-to-pay-n50-on-pos-transaction-cbn-tells-business-owners.html>
18. Oluwafemi Kayode. (July, 2021). A deep dive into the activities of PoS agents in Nigeria. July 15, 2021. Retrieved online from <https://techpoint.africa/2021/07/15/pos-business-in-nigeria/>
19. Pulse NG. March 2022. It is high time POS operations in Nigeria had massive change. Pulse Contributor's Opinion, March 10th 2022. Retrieved online from <https://www.pulse.ng/news/local/it-is-high-time-pos-operations-in-nigeria-had-massive-change-pulse-contributors/ml1m89x.amp>
20. Samuel Oyekanmi. (23 July, 2021). POS transactions in Nigeria hit over N3 trillion in H1 2021. *Nairametrics* 23 Jul 2021. Retrieved online from <https://nairametrics.com/2021/07/23/pos-transactions-in-nigeria-hit-over-n3-trillion-in-h1-2021/?amp=1>
21. Temitayo Jaiyeola. 3rd May 2022. Nigerians use PoS 178.9 million times in two months— NIBSS report. *Punch NG*. 3rd May 2022. Retrieved online from <https://punchng.com/nigerians-use-pos-178-9-million-times-in-two-months-nibss-report/?amp>
22. Tomiwa Onaleye. (April, 2021). Lagos is the PoS Capital of Nigeria with about 70% of Total Transactions Carried out in 2020. April 14, 2021. Retrieved online from

<https://technext.ng/2021/04/14/lagos-is-the-pos-capital-of-nigeria-with-about-70-of-transactions-carried-out-in-the-state/>

23. Tribune. Reps Raise Alarm Over Fraudulent POS Transactions. Retrieved online from <https://tribuneonlineng.com/rebs-raise-alarm-over-fraudulent-pos-transactions/>
24. U. Kama and M. Adigun. August 2013. Financial Inclusion In Nigeria: Issues And Challenges. Occasional Paper No. 45. Central Bank of Nigeria. Retrieved online from <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/out/2014/rtd/occasional%20paper%20no.%2045%20issues%20and%20challenges.pdf>
25. Vanguard NG. September 20, 2021. Business Ideas. How to Start A POS Business in Nigeria. Starting A POS Business In Nigeria. September 20, 2021. Retrieved online from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2021/09/business-ideas-how-to-start-a-pos-business-in-nigeria/>

A Critical Analysis of Loan Policies and Loan Recovery at a Savings and Credit Cooperative Organisation (SACCO) in Uganda: A Case of Y-Save SACCO

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Abstract:

The major objective of the study is to investigate the effect of loan policies on loan recovery in a Christian based Savings and Credit Cooperative Organisation (SACCO) using Y-Save Multipurpose Society Limited in Kampala in Uganda as a case study. Using self-administered questionnaires and interview guides data was collected from 181 respondents. Respondents were selected using purposive and random sampling techniques from a study population of 320. The study was guided by three specific objectives and three hypotheses. Loan policies are the independent variable of this study, while Loan recovery is the dependent variable. Loan policies are made up of the following attributes: Loan Appraisal policies, Loan Approval and Loan Monitoring policies. Loan recovery is made up of the following attributes: Loan Recovery Rate, Loan Loss ratio, and Portfolio at Risk. SPSS version 23 was used to run statistical analysis. The results reveal that loan policies predict the effectiveness of loan recovery though the potential is only 3.3%. Out of the three aspects of loan policies, it is loan appraisal which significantly predicts ($r= 0.276$, $p<0.05$) loan recovery. The overall recommendation is for SACCO's and Y-Save in particular, to pay special attention to loan approval processes and procedures with a view to improve loan recovery.

Keywords: Loan policies, Loan recovery, Savings and Credit Organisation

INTRODUCTION

Savings and Credit Cooperative Organisations (SACCO's) were introduced to the African continent at the Gold Coast, now Ghana, in September 1955 by an Irish-Canadian Catholic Priest known Reverend Father John McNulty. He had an idea that organisations such as SACCOs could make an important contribution to the improvement of the investment potential of the population (Emma and Maghimbi 2009).

In Uganda, The Loans Act 1965 came into force to harmonise loan and loan policies. State borrowing had policies of 'authority to borrow' and 'application for a loan' and the overall control powers of the loans' process rested with the Parliament (Chapter 236, The Loans Act 1965). In Uganda, SACCO enterprises, loan policies and loan recovery mechanisms grew more rapidly after 2001 mainly in Kampala, where small scale investors were on the rise. Nuwagaba (2012), reported about the SACCO census which was conducted in 2006 by the Ministry of Finance Planning and Economic Development, and the Department for International Development (DFID) -funded Financial Sector Deepening Unit (FSDU) project. It was revealed that in 2012, there were 1724

registered SACCOs in Uganda although only 628 could be traceable and were operational (Nuwagaba, 2012). This actually meant that many SACCO's die at infancy stage.

Among the financial institutions that first applied loan policies in Uganda was the Uganda National Police (UNP) SACCO, where loan appraisal and loan approval were strictly for the benefit of members of the UNP and their families. The concept was introduced to police units in other areas of the country. However, Nuwagaba (2012) quoted Kabuga and Batarinyebwa (1995) reporting that Christians had started formation of SACCOs in Uganda way back in 1988. The clergy especially the Catholic clerics encouraged Christians to form savings and investment groups so as to establish a lasting socio-economic structure that promoted self-initiative, self-help and self-reliance, guided by credit policies (Nantume, Daily Monitor 13 September, 2018). This is true testimony that micro finance activities have existed among Christians in Uganda for some time. These micro finance activities require sound policies and procedures to ensure good loan recovery management (Hellen and Caroline 2016).

Loan policies provide guidance on loan administration. The loan concept was, however, not appreciated until after the Second World War when it was largely taken on in Europe and later on to Africa (Investopedia). Loan portfolio constitutes the largest operating asset and source of revenue for most financial institutions (Ssekiziyivu, et al. 2017). For SACCO's, any default on loans affects financial performance and the lending potential which is very essential given the high borrower influx that characterises these SACCO's (Karim et al. 2014). This calls for good loan documentation, sound internal controls and policies including appraisal, approval and monitoring policies (FDIC Report, 2018).

Y-Save SACCO was established at a time when many Christians were finding it difficult to obtain loans from money lenders who were charging very high interest on loans, over 10% per month, which translates to 120% per annum, a rate that is too exorbitant and unaffordable. Hoda and Gupta (2014) in their studies on Loan Portfolio of faith-based institutions asserted that there was need to study the procedures and performance of religious founded financial institutions in order to ascertain their distinctive features and growth potential. According to Y-Save Annual Report 2019, there was a reported poor loan recovery performance. This thus would necessitate institution of loan policies to guide and improve on the loan recovery performance at Y-Save.

SACCOs on the onset are meant to give only short-term loans which can be fully repaid in a predetermined period (Shu-Teng et al. 2015). However, reports on loans recovery management at Y-Save indicate a number of loans in default despite the repeated reminders on repayment dates (Y- Save Annual Report, 2018). The report indicated that the loans are fully secured, but there were still challenges associated with loan rescheduling, delayed repayments and defaults. At Y-Save, it was reported that over Shs 120 million was in default as at the end of 2019, with over Shs 110 million held by one borrower (Y- Save Annual Report, 2019). SACCO services benefitting few borrowers is a high risk (Anania and Gikuri 2015), because a disaster with a single borrower can affect loan portfolio performance for the entire SACCO.

Y-Save SACCO's Annual Report of 2019 revealed a non-performing loans ratio of 4% at the close of 2019. This is high and worrying since it is higher than the maximum recommended value of 3% in microfinance institutions (Technical Guide, Washington DC, 2003; Beck et al. 2013) which has been taken as a standard in this study.

Therefore, the major objective of this research is to investigate the effect of loan policies on loan recovery at Y- Save SACCO in Kampala in Uganda. In line with the research gap of identifying the key aspect of loan policy that influences loan recovery. This research provides empirical evidence of loan appraisal as a principal aspect of loan policy that significantly affects loan recovery. Researchers like Aliija and Wakabi (2017) and Kinyera (2014) proved that loan policies affect loan recovery. However, they did not specify the component of loan policies which drives loan recovery. It is the naked gap that this study has addressed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Loan Appraisal Policies and Loan Recovery

Loan appraisal is a process performed to determine the risks associated with the extension of a loan offer to a customer (Chinduru 2016). Loan appraisal is the “heart” of a high-quality portfolio (Patience et al. 2016). Loan appraisal thus refers to finding out the repayment capacity of the borrowers with the primary purpose of ensuring safety of the money of the SACCO keeping loan losses at minimum. Thus, during loan appraisal, focus is on evaluating credit worthiness of the borrower and future expected cash flows. This is to ensure timely clearance of loan obligations (Chaplinska 2012).

The success or failure of a loan depends largely on accurate appraisal of the customers’ repayment capacity (Aliija and Wakabi 2017). It is commonly said that a loan may be bad right from the time of appraisal, to mean that a mistake committed at the time of loan appraisal will have an effect on the final loan repayment pattern. The competence of loans officers during enforcement of appraisal policies is thus paramount as this reduces the chances of lending money to non-deserving customers (Moronya et al. 2016). Chinduru (2016) concludes that appropriate loan assessment is central to controlling and minimising loan defaults.

Loan appraisal policies in financial institutions are guided by strategies and measures that are taken to guarantee smooth lending activities and loan repayments. If credit facilities are not assessed properly by competent staff guided by concrete loan appraisal policies, there is a likelihood that borrowers will default on loan repayment (Gopal and Borbora 2014). Loan appraisal policies should ensure that client relationship is preserved, if at all possible, however much they could be in default (Schicks 2011).

Loan appraisal considers loan category, membership, borrowing history, site visits, purpose of the loan, and ownership of collateral, property search, and confirmations from the employer. Nkundabanyanga et al. (2014), in their research on formal credit accessibility contend that pledging business collateral limits the firm’s ability to obtain future loans from other lenders which creates a position of power for the lenders. Many borrowers/customers who need loans report having deposited their collateral with other big financial institutions. This exposes SACCOs to borrowers who come with no titles of ownership of assets and the borrowers are in small numbers since collateral value requirement deters Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) borrowers from seeking credit. This leads to many SACCOs emphasising guarantor requirement to ensure loan recovery and smooth cash flows. Maina et al. (2018) and Ssekiziyivu et al. (2017) also in their research on credit terms and loan policies established that SMEs hesitate to seek loans until they understand why a number of requirements like guarantor and collateral are imposed on them, which ultimately results into efficient loan recovery on the side of the lender.

During loan appraisal, larger financial institutions prefer borrowers with collateral. Neuberger et al. (2011) observed that commercial banks, for example, provide larger loans, longer repayment periods and lower interest rates when borrowers offer collateral and the related loan recovery is generally good. This means that a borrower who cannot provide the type of assets, the lenders require, as collateral, often gets unfavourable loan terms as compared to the one who provides the assets in a bid to mitigate loan default risk. Neuberger et al. (2011) reasoned that due to lack of enforceable laws, collateral is essential in SACCO lending noting that borrowers who provide more collateral receive a better rating than their disadvantaged counterparts. Access to finance is particularly difficult for SMEs whenever there is insufficient collateral. Thus, assets pledged as collateral together with social collateral (guarantors) are believed to be key determinants of loan recovery performance (GoodLuck and Neema 2016).

SACCOs and more so Christian based SACCOs always have majority of their customers as low-income earners (Mphaka 2017). Some borrowers struggle to pay back and some even end up borrowing from other lenders which exposes the SACCO to a high default risk. These side money lenders always give out loans at high interest rates (Goldin and Tatiana 2013) and this lowers the borrower's capacity to repay which has a negative impact on general loan recovery rate.

Portfolio at risk as an indicator of loan quality is the key determinant of competition, survival and profitability of SACCOs. The basis of credit rating approach is to guide the lender to decide either to accept or reject an application so as to mitigate risks associated with credit appraisal (Gaitho 2010). Loan policies assist in decision making by establishing what would be the best rule to apply on a sample of applicants. Credit rating allows for case by case risk management assessment when appraising a loan applicant. It therefore refers to the use of statistical models to transform relevant data into numerical measures that guide credit decisions. Thus, credit rating as a process, is referred to as the industrialization of trust, aiming at improvement of loan quality. However, volunteer founder board members of SACCOs tend to interfere in the operations even after the professional management has been put in place (Kibui and Moronge 2014). These policies and the related practices are key towards micro-loan portfolio quality and control of credit risk for sustainable loan recovery. These policies should not be mere written down statements but should be adaptive to the changing economic environment to foster SACCO growth (Omeke et al. 2019)

Loan Approval Policies and Loan Recovery

A loan approval policy is an institutional method for analysing credit requests and the decision criteria for accepting or rejecting loan applications (Girma 2018). Loan approval requires the applicant to fill the application form indicating the desired loan amount, the purpose for the loan, collateral and guarantors' particulars. According to Y-Save lending policies and guidelines, a guarantor should be a customer in good standing, with no reported cases of loan default and with capacity to pay in case of default by the borrower. Whereas most loan transactions are manually processed, Gordon and McCarthy (2014) support online loan transactions and processing and contend that it helps ensuring that responsible lenders compete and it also expands access to credit with improved efficiency in loan recovery. As per the lending policy guidelines at Y-Save, loan approval policies include; powers to approve, signed loan application/agreement, consent to the terms and conditions of the loan agreement, acceptance and adoption of the loan repayment schedule. Loan policies and loan recovery form a big part of the activities of Christian based SACCOs which offer loan facilities and savings as key financial services rendered to the people to help them overcome poverty (Anania and Gikuri 2015).

Among the first studies on loan business were by Keeton and Morris in 1987 where loan losses were used as main indicators of problem loans (Khemraj and Pasha 2009). Borrowers tend to prefer short term salary loans instead of long-term loans secured on their assets for fear of losing their assets in case of inability to pay back (Annika 2017). Abaidoo and Shadrach (2015), in their research, underscored the relevance of loan terms and conditions governing loans payable at some future date as governed by a legal contract. The conditions involve payment of interest on the loan, although some of these loans end up in default where the borrower is unable to fulfil his/her loan obligations as and when due and thus problem loans and loan losses. SACCOs as Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) provide financial services to low income as well as unbanked clientele who otherwise would have no access to financial services (Mpiira et al. 2013). This function necessitates having refined loan approval policies so as to guarantee good loan recovery rates to enable growth of the financial institution (Ssekiziyivu et al. 2017). However, Maithya (2017) in his research found that loan policies had insignificant effect on financial performance of church based SACCOs, recommending regular reviews if Church based SACCOs are to remain competitive.

Watoto Church which founded Y-Save is predominantly youth, females and males alike, although the annual reports 2018 showed males dominating the borrowing. Awunyo (2013), in her study found that the chance of a loan repayment was higher for males than for the females adding that male borrowers had more experience in accessing microcredit than their female counterparts. On the contrary, Abdul and Roslan (2009) had investigated microcredit loan repayment in Malaysia and in their research; they found that male borrowers who had a longer duration for repayments had a higher probability of defaulting. According to Abdul and Roslan (2009) and Miller (2014) borrowers involved in non-production-oriented business activities such as the service or the support sectors, but with training in their particular business had lower probabilities of defaulting. The use of credit rating policies therefore has positive effects on the number of approved loans to small businesses (Neuberger et al. 2011).

According to Gatuhu (2013), factors that affect loan recovery performance evolve around improper appraisal by credit officers and at times lack of willingness to repay loans, coupled with diversion of funds by borrowers. This view is also shared by Anderson and Gascon (2009), which calls for vigilance in the recruitment of loans officers to ensure that committed and competent staff is engaged. Loan policies therefore help to decide which customers qualify for loans, the exact payment terms, the limits set on outstanding balances and how to deal with delinquent accounts (Twesige 2021). MFIs need a monetary system that highlights repayment problems clearly and quickly so that loan committees and management can focus on delinquency before it gets out of hand.

The researcher investigated whether loan approval puts into consideration the repayment history and whether this has impact on loan recovery. For long, successful loan recovery managers have had to focus their efforts on credit rating and careful loan monitoring/evaluation and approval procedures. This allows SACCOs to ensure that loans are paid on time and in case of delinquency warning signs can easily be detected (Ndiege et al. 2016). Loan evaluation as a stage of the approval process includes among others; Evidence of income, two credible guarantors, tenure of membership, loan repayment history, savings account holder and location of applicant's residence. The information on the borrower enables SACCOs to easily monitor loan performance so as to maximise returns to a loan portfolio investment, the main source of income, while keeping the credit risk low (Riza et al. 2015). Loan policies are essential for smooth growth of any

SACCO and help at the management of credit risk so as to lower potential losses from loan defaults and thus allowing expansion of operations (Mphaka 2017). This notwithstanding, Chikamai and Mutua (2018) in their research, found a positive but insignificant impact of loan policies on loan performance amongst SACCOs in Kakamega County, Kenya.

Christian based SACCOs do not operate under the credit reference bureau, and like any other SACCOs in Uganda, they are not regulated by the Central Bank (Nuwagaba 2012). This puts SACCOs to a disadvantage, of inability to discover their financial challenges timely, which accumulates to a big problem in the long run. SACCOs are therefore more vulnerable to loan default with some borrowers obtaining many other loans from other lenders due to absence of a central control (Nzomo 2017), and this affects loan repayment performance. Korankye (2014) in his studies on multiple borrowing and loan recovery, asserted that loan approval policies are essential because they improve loan recovery rates by screening the clients' loan applications to assess credit worthiness. Loan policies are therefore important in the management of the SACCO's accounts receivables and the quality of loans is a key determinant of the institutions' survival and profitability (Mwangi and Wanjau 2013).

The SACCO's adaptive behaviour through loan policies and the resultant positive effect on loan recovery is important for the growth of any micro credit institution (Omeke, et al., 2019). Credit management is key for any financial institution to grow and revenue from interest on loans contributes the bigger percentage to the overall profitability of the lending firm (Agu et al. 2013). According to Nuwagaba (2012), loan appraisal and approval policies are conducted at Masaka Microfinance and Development Cooperative Trust Limited (MAMIDECOT) right from sensitization through application, then verification of collateral and ascertainment of ability to pay back before approval. This should be the norm since it provides a track of loan follow up and loan recovery performance (Faical 2014).

Loan Monitoring Policies and Loan Recovery

For any lending institution to continue providing credit services, it must be able to sustain a defined loan collection threshold as is adequate to meet recurrent expenditure. For good loan recovery process, the manager and the borrower agree on the repayment period basing on the purpose of the loan and nature of business. The lender would expect to collect both principal and interest according to the loan repayment schedule and at the least cost of loan recovery process (Khieu et al. 2012). This however may not be the case always, as a number of loans are always in default of some days. An individual loan is typically declared to be in default if payment is 270 days late (investopedia.com). Default rate is the percentage of all outstanding loans that a lender has written off after a prolonged period of missed payments. The standard loan default rate, as an indicator of loan portfolio quality, is set at a maximum of 3% for good performance of a SACCO going by international standards (Beck et al. 2013). Default rates therefore that exceed 3% pose a threat to both capital and profitability of any lending institution, especially if the default rate goes way above the 3% tolerable maximum (Korankye 2014).

To be financially sustainable, MFIs should invest in high quality loan assets with high portfolio quality based on 100% repayment or at worst low delinquency, low-cost loan recovery and efficient lending (Anderson and Gascon, 2009). However, a number of loans with SACCOs are always rescheduled to a period beyond the originally agreed dates, a number of them experiencing increased Portfolio at Risk (IFAD Report, 2016). In his research Ndikubwimana (2018), found that better loan monitoring and management in microfinance institutions led to

improved loan recovery performance. Application of relevant loan policies is therefore helpful at credit management in SACCOs.

Loan monitoring systems include open and free communication between the lender and borrower together with good record keeping and automation of the loan tracking system (Tijjani 2016). Under loan monitoring, the study undertook to establish loan performance of the SACCO after loan disbursement to various borrowers. This also explains how loans are scheduled and how they are actually performing in terms of planned repayment schedules compared to actual repayments (Okiror 2018). Loan monitoring is thus closely associated with timely and steady repayment of interest and principal of a loan. Default on borrowed funds arises from unfavourable circumstances that vary according to the type, timing and size of business/industry which affects loan recovery (Mariusz et al. 2018). Under monitoring policies, the nature and state of investments that borrowers undertake are also investigated so as to establish profitability and guarantee loan repayments. Therefore, loan monitoring by following up loan repayments is vital since delinquency trends affect financial performance (Zainuddin and Yasin 2019).

Loan monitoring policies at Y-Save are derived from policy on eligibility of borrowers, policy on loan details (size, period, instalment, and interest), policy on penalties and security. These policies are a means through which the financial institutions ensure that the lending function is operating within established risk tolerances. Loan policies and procedures aligned with mission and objectives serve as a framework for major credit decisions and actions of a financial institution (Adams 2014). Most SACCO loans, especially in the rural set ups, are agricultural with semi-illiterate customers. These rural based loans require a lot of monitoring as compared to those of Y-Save where a number of them are educational, and the borrowers are dominantly literate youths (Ssekiziyivu et al. 2017). Mohd (2013) in his research found out that good religious background, level of education and level of income contribute greatly to the reduction of loan default. With appropriate loan monitoring policies, Christian based SACCOs would therefore be in position to have low loan default rates. Kibrom (2010) also in his research established that purpose of loan and types of labour were key determinants of loan recovery performance.

In his research, Wilson (2007), presented a systematic understanding of the causes of loan default and identified the major causes as unprofitable business, high interest rate and poor supervision among others. Hoda and Gupta (2014), in their study of loan portfolio of faith based SACCOs found that the failure of a number of faith based micro financial institutions is largely due to their inability to ensure good repayment by borrowers, coupled by poor governance of staff who are not professionally trained to manage credit. This argument is also supported by Yong and Mwase (2012) in their studies on development financing. SACCO board members sometimes guarantee loans given to their relatives but such borrowers are not committed to the repayment plan which affects the loan recovery rate and loan portfolio quality yet the sustainability of microfinance institutions depends largely on their ability to collect loans as efficiently and effectively as possible (Gyimah 2019).

Loan monitoring thus involves keeping borrowers' records and providing technical support to the borrowers. It also involves maintaining a healthy relationship with the borrowers, giving repayment reminders seven days to the due date. Loan monitoring also involves engaging the guarantors and designing strategies to recover loans in default, which necessitates frequent contact with borrowers (Moody's Analytics, 2018). This creates an environment where the lender is a problem solver and a trusted advisor to the borrower rather than a mere funds provider. This

builds a culture of being supportive to borrowers whenever they are found to be in difficulty, especially with project supervision and investment appraisal by dealing with investment problems together (Mwangi, 2013). The loan policies may also require continuous review so that they are adaptive to the ever-changing repayment trends of borrowers (Clement et al. 2013). Difficulty with the borrowers can be detected from the repayment trend, when the instalments are delayed or when a repayment is below the scheduled amount. SACCOs have to follow up the loans to ensure recovery before the loans become delinquent and this ought to be a full-time activity under the SACCO's administration since supervision is one of the key factors at improving loan recovery (Claudia et al. 2019).

Loan monitoring schemes with competent staff is essential because an inadequate financial analysis skill is another cause of loan default, yet it can be dealt with through these monitoring schemes (Sheila 2011). Some loan clients may even disappear due to poor business practices, which calls for strict adherence to the loan policies rather than trust, as is characteristic of Christian based SACCOs (Maithya 2017). Such situations require SACCOs to institute coordinated loan performance monitoring systems. Many borrowers could be lacking technical skills like record keeping and supervisory skills which are essential for successful business (Anania and Gikuri 2015). SACCOs are today getting upset due to poor loan management skills and borrowers at times do not separate the borrowed funds from their other finances which lead to financial mismanagement (Okori, 2018). Other borrowers do not plough back the profit which also leads to cash flow challenges and loan default in the long run (Clement 2013).

Moti (2012) in their research on the relationship between credit management system and loan performance considered credit terms, client appraisal, credit risk control and collection policy as key variables influencing loan performance where the 5Cs namely; capacity, character, collateral, capital and condition were used to appraise clients. The clients' cash flows were also a critical factor for consistent loan repayments. For SACCOs to make good loan recoveries, borrowers should be subjected to pressure to reduce cases of delayed repayments and defaults (Nawai and Mohd 2013). It is believed that some borrowers default strategically especially if the cost of strategic default is low given the low collateral requirement. This strategic default together with the lenient loan recovery procedures characteristic of Christian based SACCOs and the legal systems giving little powers to enforce contracts affects loan recovery (Kinyera 2014).

Loan monitoring would indeed work out very well by providing technical advice where need arises and coming up with policies that carry enforceable contracts. Technical training on microfinance investments and exposure to wider entrepreneurial environments cushions the loans against start-up challenges and enables investment growth which in effect improves loan recovery (Nguta and Huka 2013).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theories underlying this study are as follows:

The Agency Theory

The Agency theory applies where there is distinction between ownership and management of a business. Agency theory was developed by Stephen Ross and Barry Mitnick in the 1970s. The theory explains the relationship between agents (management) and the principal who are the shareholders/owners of the SACCO under study. The agent represents the principal in the SACCO transactions and in the best business interest of the principal without regard to self-interest.

According to this theory, a SACCO comprises two stakeholders; Management and the shareholders, and a SACCO being an artificial person interacts and enters into loan contracts with other entities but guided by loan policies (Mugo 2015).

This theory contends that there is a clear established boundary between the agent and the owner. The role of the agent is mainly that of governing the activities of the SACCO through the design and innovation of investment options. The SACCO owners/shareholders on the other hand expect management to make and enforce policies which should govern the financial institution for the benefit of owners' interests in line with the agency theory and in regard to the economic exchange relations between principal and agent (Opala 2014). The SACCO as a financial institution, with the lending business being the main revenue activity has to engage the stakeholders for practical and enforceable loan policies.

The agency theory thus defines the role of various stakeholders as pertaining to ownership and control of an entity, where the running of the business is delegated to the managers and other employees (Kibs 2019). The theory thus offers a variety of ways to examine the relationship between SACCO owners and management staff, putting mechanisms on how the final objective of maximising returns to the owners can be achieved.

However, this theory has been criticised for being hardly subject to empirical test and being unrealistically one sided because of its neglect of potential exploitation of workers (Brahmadev and Leepsa 2017). The limitations to the agency theory calls for modifications in areas of agents' motivations and risk evasiveness. This prompted the application of the liquidity preference theory which would mitigate the credit risk, one of the major risks for SACCOs, and cover such gaps.

Liquidity Preference Theory

In macroeconomic theory, liquidity preference is the demand for money, considered as liquidity. According to Jane (2017), liquidity has a strong influence on financial performance of saving and credit societies. The liquidity theory was first developed by John Maynard Keynes in 1936. As a macroeconomic theory, it applies very well to SACCOs since their operations spread across the entire national economy with very many loan applicants/borrowers, and in most cases these borrowers have not saved enough funds to meet the qualifications for loan application.

Finance is the lifeblood of financial institutions of any kind or size. Liquidity, which is exhibited by optimal financial resources on hand, is of great concern to the modern era SACCOs, the likes of Y-Save, and management ought to put in place appropriate financial management policies to limit and control material sources of liquidity risk (Githaka et al. 2017). The high demand for loans at Y-Save, as per the liquidity theory, tends to set high interest rates driven by the supply and demand for money. This may affect the repayment trends, many borrowers later complaining of the exorbitant interest rates which may lead to a number of loans becoming delinquent (Korankye 2014).

As the number of loan applicants multiplies, the application of stringent loan policies in examining credit risk and the associated factors becomes imperative. Robert Merton (1974), in his credit risk theory, brings out the factors that increase the risk of a debtor failing to meet punctually the financial commitments stemming from loan agreements. It is reasoned that interest rate increments which at times arise from loan policies and agreements are likely to cause loan defaults with SACCOs (Consultative Group to Assist the Poor, 2009). However, one of the

limitations of the liquidity theory is the determination of interest rate which management under the Agency theory would resolve by applying best practices (Brahmadev and Leepsa 2017).

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Based on the literature review and conceptual framework, the following null research hypotheses were formulated:

- H1: There is no significant effect of Loan Appraisal Policies on Loan Recovery at Y-Save SACCO.
- H2: There is no significant effect of Loan Approval Policies on Loan Recovery at Y-Save SACCO.
- H3: There is no significant effect of Loan Monitoring Policies on Loan Recovery at Y-Save SACCO.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample and Data Selection

Data for this study were collected using self-administered questionnaires and interviews.

A sample size of 181 participants out of a population of 320 active members was selected in accordance with Krejcie and Morgan 1970 Tables for determining sample size for research activities. Respondents were selected as shown in Table 1 below, with a bigger category contributing a larger number of respondents (Fairbairn and Kessler 2015).

Table 1: Study population categories

Category	Employees	Board members	Borrowers	Total Population
Number	8	10	302	320

Source: Primary data

Purposive sampling method was used to select board members and employees given their numbers and deemed to be in possession of critical information by virtue of their knowledge and experience with the SACCO (Creswell 2014 and Etikan 2016). Random sampling was used to select borrowers given their large numbers and to avoid bias. The population was identified, which was a register, and a sampling frame developed where a list of the prospective respondents was developed and each of the 302 prospective respondents were assigned a random number to make ballots for sample selection. Then 163 ballots were randomly drawn constituting the 163 prospective respondents. Questionnaires were then administered and a total of 163 questionnaires were received back, representing 100 percent response rate.

Table 2. Sampling technique and sample size

Category	Employees	Board members	Borrowers	Total sample
Sample size	8	10	163	181
Sampling Technique	Purposive Sampling	Purposive Sampling	Simple Random Sampling	

Source: Primary data

Reliability of the Scales

The reliability of the two scales of loan policies and loan recovery were determined by Cronbach's alpha coefficient as generated by SPSS. The results indicate that for all the two variables, the

coefficients are above the threshold of 60% as recommended by Ursachi et al. (2013). Accordingly, it was concluded that the scales for measuring loan policies and loan recovery were all reliable (Table 3).

Table 3. Reliability analysis statistics for the study variables

Variables	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Number of Items
Loan Approval Policies	77.5%	10
Loan Appraisal Policies	86.9%	10
Loan Monitoring Policies	81.3%	10
Loan Recovery Aspects	90.6%	10

Validity of the Instruments

Validity is the extent to which an instrument measures what it is supposed to measure and performs as it is designed to perform. It refers to the truthfulness of findings, accuracy and quality of the instrument used to collect data. Validity of the instrument takes both the content and external validity.

Content validity refers to the appropriateness of the content of an instrument and for this study, it was measured by the Content Validity Ratio (CVR), where professionals who are subject matter experts were selected to constitute a panel to evaluate whether test items of the data collection instrument related to the research objectives or not. Eight (8) people were selected to constitute the panel for this evaluation. The formula for CVR below was used;

$$CVR = \frac{n_e - \frac{N}{2}}{\frac{N}{2}} \text{ where } N = \text{total number of people on the panel and}$$

n_e = number of people on panel indicating essential

A negative score means that the item lacks validity while a positive score means that there is some degree of validity. The higher the score, the higher the item validity.

$$\text{Overall CVR} = \frac{\sum CVR \text{ for individual items}}{\text{Total no of items on the instrument}} = \frac{28.75}{40} = 0.71875 = 72\% .$$

Overall, the average CVR for all the items was 0.720. This score of 0.720 or 72.0%, represented content validity according to Lawshe (1975), where a score of 0.50 or more is sufficient enough for content validity (Rodrigues et al. (2017); Collin and Scally, 2013). At 72.0% the items of the data collection tool were therefore predicted to validly measure the intended variables.

External validity is the extent to which the results of a study can be generalized from a sample to a population. Establishing external validity was achieved through sampling. First, a section of active borrowers was established. This would mean that any random sample now selected would be representative of the entire population. With board members and staff, all of them were involved in the study. Through purposive and simple random sampling, and by the fact that the

sample took a good fraction of the target population, external validity was enshrined. External validity helped to obtain population generalizability, or the degree to which a sample represented the population.

Measurement of Variables

In order to tap the domain of loan policies, the model used by Aromorach (2013) was adopted. Accordingly, loan policies dimensions include the following: loan appraisal policies, loan approval policies, and loan monitoring policies. In order to tap the domain of loan recovery the model used by Hoda and Gupta (2014) was adopted. The following dimensions were used: loan recovery rate, loan loss rate, and portfolio at risk. Notably, all the dimensions were anchored on a five point Likert scale (1-5) ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

Data Processing and Analysis

The study employed quantitative techniques in data analysis. Data from the questionnaires were subjected to the Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS). SPSS was used for coding, editing and analysis. Descriptive statistics arising from SPSS manipulation of data from questionnaires are presented. Correlation analysis was done to generate coefficients in order to determine the direction and extent of relation of study variables. Regression analysis was performed in order to ascertain the predictive potential of the independent variable (loan policies) on the dependent variable (loan recovery).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the descriptive statistics of the respondents, results of the correlation and regression analyses, conclusion, recommendations, and limitations of the study and areas of further research.

Descriptive Statistics of the Respondents

Table 4. Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	78	47.9	47.9
Female	85	52.1	100.0
Total	163	100.0	

Source: Primary data, n=163

The table above shows that 52.1% of respondents were female, while 47.9% were male. Thus, the sample was gender sensitive as gender was one of the intervening variables.

Age of the Respondents

Table 5. Age of the respondents

Age description	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 25 years	2	1.2	1.2
between 25 and 40 years inclusive	55	33.7	35.0
between 40 to 50 years	67	41.1	76.1
above 50 years	39	23.9	100.0
Total	163	100.0	

Source: Primary data, n=163

The above table shows that the biggest percentage of respondents lies between the age range of 25 to 50 years old constituting 74.8% of the respondents. These findings meant that majority of respondents at Y-Save SACCO were mature and in a hardworking and energetic/employable age range, which predicts that these respondents were more likely to repay back their loans given the sense of responsibility that comes with age (Murthy and Mariadas 2017).

Time spent as members of Y-Save SACCO

Time spent as members of the SACCO was also selected as a factor that could affect loan recovery.

Table 6. Time respondents have spent as members of Y-Save SACCO

Age description	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
less than 1 year	2	1.2	1.2
between 1 and 2 years inclusive	7	4.3	5.5
above 2 but below 3 years	10	6.1	11.7
3 years and above	144	88.3	100.0
Total	163	100.0	

Source: Primary data, n=163

The table above shows the time respondents have spent as members of Y-Save SACCO. It indicates that 144 out of 163 respondents, representing 88.3%, have been members of the SACCO for more than three years. The results actually showed a significant relationship between membership with the SACCO and loan recovery. A longer period of saving with the SACCO is correlated to client and employee loyalty. The longer period clients stay with the SACCO also enables staff to improve relationship and know more about these clients before disbursing loans. The findings revealed that the majority of borrowers have been members of the SACCO for long, showing that respondents were likely to repay their loans provided their credit history was good and sustainable.

Respondents' Level of Education

The level of education was considered to have an effect on loan recovery.

Table 7. Respondents' level of education

Educational status	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
No formal Education	1	0.6	0.6
Uganda Advanced Certificate of Education	10	6.1	6.7
Diploma	24	14.7	21.5
University Degree	128	78.5	100.0
Total	163	100.0	

Source: Primary data, n=163

Table 7 above shows respondents' level of education where 78.5% of the respondents have a university degree. Thus, the sample is predominantly degree holders. Results however showed that level of education is non-significant towards loan recovery. As a unit increase in the level of

education is predicted to decrease loan recovery by 0.043 units. High education therefore may not necessarily mean success in business investments.

Descriptive Statistics of Modes of Loan Recovery

The modes of loan recovery were studied to find out whether loan recovery process is smooth or whether it involved force.

Table 8. Modes of loan recovery

Recovery technique	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Savings	117	76.4	76.4
Guarantor	6	3.9	80.3
Seized collateral	28	18.3	98.6
Arbitration	1	0.7	99.3
Court Action	1	0.7	100.0
Total	153	93.9	
Non response	10	6.1	
	163	100.0	

Source: Primary data, n=163

Table 8 above shows responses on modes of loan recovery. The respondents repay most of the loan funds by use of savings, with over 76.4% of them relying on the savings to repay loans. There were 10 respondents who did not respond to this question.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the extent/degree and direction of the relationship between the study variables.

Table 9. Correlation analysis results between loan policies and loan recovery

	Loan Recovery Aspects	Loan Approval Policies	Loan Appraisal Policies	Loan Monitoring Policies
Loan Recovery Aspects	1	-.117	.014	-.129
Loan Approval Policies	-.117	1	.738**	.598**
Loan Appraisal Policies	.014	.738**	1	.601**
Loan Monitoring Policies	-.129	.598**	.601**	1
	.136	.136	.000	.000
	.864	.864	.000	.000
	.102	.000	.000	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Primary data, n=163

The results presented in Table 9 indicate the following:

- (i) That there is a weak negative relation between loan approval policies and loan recovery at -0.117
- (ii) That there is a weak positive relation between loan appraisal policies and loan recovery at 0.014
- (iii) That there is a weak negative relation between loan monitoring policies and loan recovery.

The implication of these results is that engaging resources in loan approval policies is likely to only cause an expense with no economic benefits. Thus approval policies do not necessarily improve loan recovery and the costs incurred in implementation of approval policies may not be recoverable. The weak positive relationship between loan appraisal policies and loan recovery means that there is little benefit derived from appraisal policies as far as loan recovery is concerned. The inverse relationship between loan monitoring policies and loan recovery may result in a situation whereby the costs incurred in implementation of loan monitoring policies are not recovered (Schober 2018). This may imply that funds spent on loan monitoring policies have no causal effect on the loan recovery performance. This is supported by Maithya (2017) whose research found that loan policies had insignificant effect on financial performance of church based SACCO's.

Regression Analysis

This study was based on three hypotheses namely:

H₁: There is no significant effect of Loan Appraisal Policies on Loan Recovery at Y-Save SACCO.

H₂: There is no significant effect of Loan Approval Policies on Loan Recovery at Y-Save SACCO.

H₃: There is no significant effect of Loan Monitoring Policies on Loan Recovery at Y-Save SACCO.

The results in Table 10 indicate that the combined effect of the independent variable dimensions (loan approval, loan appraisal and loan monitoring) have the power of only 3.3% in explaining changes in the dependent variable (loan recovery). This means that 96.7% of loan recovery performance may be explained by the intervening and other variables not covered in the study. Mustafa, Muturi and Samantar (2019) found that loan recovery performance depended primarily on borrowers' characteristics which are more or less external to the SACCO, other than the loan policies. Thus, within the scope of this study, loan policies insignificantly affect loan recovery at Y-Save.

Table 10. Model Summary of Loan Policies on Loan Recovery

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.225 ^a	.051	.033	.52631
a. Predictors: (Constant), Loan Monitoring Policies, Loan Approval Policies, and Loan Appraisal policies				

The results in Table 10 indicate the following:

The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant effect of loan appraisal policies on loan recovery can be rejected. This is because the beta in this case is 0.276 at the significance of 0.023 which is less than 5%. Findings from interviews were such that most interviewees indicated that the major challenge encountered in loan recovery was unprofitable businesses. This may mean that at the appraisal stage there are gaps and the activities that would generate funds to pay off the loans extended to the borrowers are left out. However most interviewees stated that the major mode of recovery of loans in default is by collateral and savings which may be attributable

to appraisal policies. This is also highlighted in their reported increase in the loan recovery rate over the period 2016 to 2019. These findings are in line with those of Osei (2015) who in his research found that relevant credit appraisal policies improve loan recovery performance.

The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant effect of loan approval policies on loan recovery cannot be rejected. This is because the beta in this case is -0.226 at the significance of 0.06 which is above 5%. From the interviews, most interviewees indicated that one of the major requirements for borrowers is that a borrower should have stayed with the SACCO for at least 6 months according to the approval policies. Borrowers are also required to have savings and a substantive guarantor to qualify for credit. Majority of the interviewees indicated that the outstanding borrowers have stayed with the SACCO for over three years and fulfilled the savings and guarantor requirements. However, the same interviewees acknowledged that there are always loans past due dates even after following the approval requirements to the letter. This supports the non-rejection of this hypothesis since approval policies seem not to impact on the loan recovery. This is in agreement with Gatuhu (2013) who found out that factors that affect loan recovery performance evolve around improper appraisal and approval by credit officers.

The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant effect of loan monitoring policies on loan recovery cannot be rejected. This is because the beta in this case is -0.160 at the significance of 0.116 which is above 5%. The regression model is at 5% level of significance. From the interviews, most of the interviewees revealed that they hold monthly loan committee meetings and submit quarterly reports to the board on loan performance. The interviewees reported loan defaults and delinquencies, meaning that the monitoring policies may not have been as effective *as they should have been*. The findings are supported by research by Hoda and Gupta (2014) who in their study on loan portfolio of faith based SACCOs found that the failure of a number of faith based micro financial institutions is largely due to their inappropriate loan monitoring mechanisms.

Table 11. Regression Coefficients of Loan Policies on Loan Recovery

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constants)	4.659	.289		16.145	.000
	Loan Appraisal Policies	.239	.104	.276	2.303	.023
	Loan Approval Policies	-.204	.108	-.226	-1.888	.061
	Loan Monitoring Policies	-.141	.089	-.160	-1.582	.116

a. Dependent Variable: Loan Recovery Aspects

Source: Primary data, n=163

CONCLUSION

From the presentation, analysis and discussion the findings above, it can be concluded that there is agreement between the findings from both primary and secondary data. Respondents to questionnaires and those who participated in interviews shared common grounds as far as the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable was concerned. Analysis of data from both primary and secondary sources did not differ significantly. The overall correlation between the loan policies and loan recovery was very weak. The findings show that there is no

significant effect of loan policies on loan recovery as loan policies had the power of only 3.3% in explaining changes in the dependent variable (loan recovery) leaving 96.7% to be explained by the intervening and other variables not covered in the study.

Despite the fact that this study has made some contributions to literature, it has some limitations which provide avenues for further research. Given that the study was limited to a case study which may not have all features of other SACCOs, generalizability of the study may be limited. Future studies should therefore consider using other research strategies.

The following recommendations are worth mentioning:

- There should be a review of loan policies to make them more effective towards loan recovery processes. This may be through increased training and research in loan policy making and implementation. This will enhance the competences and knowledge in the making, review and implementation of loan approval, appraisal and monitoring policies.
- Since loan policies have little influence on loan recovery at Christian based SACCOs, it is necessary to give the SACCOs autonomy to enforce policy.
- Basing on the Agency Theory, employees and management who implement loan policies should have a stake in the sharing of profits generated from interest on credit. This improves their sense of belonging and they would probably be prompted to implement and ensure effectiveness of loan policies on loan recovery.

Further research should consider the following areas:

- Other factors other than loan policies need to be investigated in relation to loan recovery performance since this study was limited to loan policies and how they affect loan recovery.
- Future studies should consider factors such as level of individual honesty, faithfulness, economic environment, inflation, political ideology, national security and management of the SACCO together with other factors which have been left out and could have impact on loan recovery at Christian based SACCO's and other SACCO's

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests

REFERENCES

- Abaidoo, A. and Oppong, S., 2015. Determinants of Loan Default and its effects on Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Ghana. A Case of Fidelity Bank Limited, Munich, GRIN Verlag, <https://www.grin.com/document/373126>
- Abdul, K. and Roslan, H. K., 2009. Determinants of Microcredit Repayment in Malaysia. The case of Agrobank. *Humanity and Social Sciences Journal*
- Adams, J. L., 2014. Development and Maintenance of an Effective Loan Policy. *Community Banking Connections. The Federal Reserve System*. Available at: <https://www.communitybankingconnections.org>
- Agu, O.C. et al., 2013. Credit Management and Bad Debt in Nigeria Commercial Bank – Implications for Development. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science* Volume 12, Issue 3 pp. 47-56
- Aliija, R. and Wakabi, B., 2017. The Effect of Loan Appraisal Process Management on Credit Performance in Microfinance Institutions (MFIs): A case of MFIs in Uganda. *International Journal of Science and Research Vol. 6, Issue 4: 6-391 April 2017*. Mountains of the Moon University.

- Anania, P. and Gikuri, A., 2015. SACCOs and Members Expectations: Factors Affecting SACCOs Capacity to Meet Members' Expectations. Moshi Co-operative University, Tanzania. *Workshop Proceedings of the Cooperative Research Workshop*. Publisher: Journal of Cooperative and Business Studies.
- Anderson, R. G. and Gascon, C.S., 2009. *The Commercial Paper Market, The Federal Reserve System and the 2007—2009 Financial Crisis*. New York. McGrawHill.
- Annika, N., 2017. Housing Finance Kampala: *To Borrow or Not to Borrow*. KTH Centre for banking and Finance. SE-100 44 Stockholm, Sweden.
- Aromorach, P., 2013. *Credit Management Policies and Loan Portfolio Performance in Commercial Banks: A Case of Equity Bank, Adjumani Branch, Uganda*. Uganda Management Institute. Available at: umispace.umi.ac.ug
- Awunyo, V. 2013. *Factors Affecting Loan Performance Among Yam Farmers in the Sene District of Ghana*. Agris On-line Papers in Economics and Informatics June 2013. Kwame Nkrumah University of Science & Technology. Ghana. Vol. V No. 2, 2013 p119.
- Beck, R. Jakubit, P. Anamaria, P., 2013. Non-Performing Loans. *What matters in Addition to the Economic Cycle*. Working Paper Series No.1515, Feb 2013. European Central Bank.
- Chikamai, L.V. Mutua, M., 2018. Effect of Credit Policy on Financial Performance of Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies in Kakamega County, Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*. Vol. 5, Iss.4 pp. 1378-1395.
- Chinduru, P. 2016. *Impact of Credit Appraisal Techniques on Microfinances' Loan Performance*. National University of Science and Technology. Available at: <https://www.academia.edu>
- Claudia, G. et al., 2019. The impact of lending standards on default rates of residential real estate loans. *European Central Bank*. Occasional Paper Series No 220/ March 2019.
- Clement, O. O. Jagongo, A. & Mbewa, M. O., 2013. The Contribution of Sacco Financial Stewardship to Growth of Saccos in Kenya. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Centre for Promoting Idea, USA. Vol. 3 No. 17, September 2013.
- Collin, A. and Scally, A. J., 2013. Critical Values for Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio: Revisiting the Original Methods of Calculation. *Measurement and Evaluation in Counselling and Development 2014*. Vol 47(1) 79-86. Online; mecd.sagepub.com. SAGE
- Creswell, J. W., 2014. Research Design. *Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches*, Fourth Edition. SAGE Publications, Inc. Online: <https://www.scrip.org>
- Emma, A. and Maghimbi, S., 2009. African Cooperatives and the Financial Crisis. *The Cooperative Facility for Africa*. International Labour Organisation. Coop^{Africa} Working Paper No.3
- Etikan, I., 2016. Comparison of Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*. Near East University. Science Publishing Group. Vol. 5, No. 1, 2016 pp 1-4 DOI: 10.11648/j.ajtas.20160501.11
- Faical, B., 2014. *Loan Quality Determinants: Evaluating the contribution of Bank-specific variables, macroeconomic factors and firm level information*. The Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies, Working Paper, No.04/2014 ECONSTOR. Geneva. Available at:<http://hdl.handle.net/10419/122102>
- Fairbairn, W. and Kessler, A., 2015. Practical Advice for Selecting Sample Sizes. *The Donor Committee for Enterprise Development (DCED)*
- Gaitho, M., 2010. A Survey of Credit risk Management Practices by SACCOs in Nairobi. Nairobi University. Wadsworth

- Gatuhu, R. N., 2013. The Effect of Credit Management on the Financial Performance of Microfinance Institutions in Kenya. University of Nairobi.
- Girma, G. J., 2018. Determinants of Loan Repayment: The Case of Microfinance Institutions in Gedeo Zone, SNNPRS, Ethiopia. Universal. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*. 6(3): 108-122, 2018. Dilla University, Ethiopia
- Githaka, J. M, Maina, K. E. and Gachora, S., 2017. Effect of Liquidity Management on Liquidity of Savings and Credit Co-operative Societies in Kirinyaga county, Kenya. University of Embu, Kenya. *International Academic Journal of Economics and Finance*, Volume 2, Issue 3, pp. 57-73
- Goldin, G. and Tatiana, H., 2013. *Consumer Borrowing after Pay Day Loan Bans*. Princeton University, Industrial Relations Section, Princeton, NJ 08544-2098
- GoodLuck, C. and Neema, G. M., 2016. Effects of Collateral On Loan Repayment: Evidence From an Informal Lending Institution. *Journal of African Business* 17(2):254-272. University of Dar es Salaam.
- Gopal, K. and Borbora, S., 2014. Loan Recovery Performance of Credit Officers in Microfinance Institutions: A Case of Assam, *International Journal of Science and Research*, Volume 3 Issue 9, September 2014. B.B.K College – India
- Gordon, K. M. and McCarthy, B., 2014. The State of Small Business Lending: *Credit Access during the Recovery and how Technology may change the Game*. Harvard Business School.
- Gyimah, F. S., 2019. Borrower – Lender Relationship and Access to Commercial Banks' Credit Market. *Journal of sustainable finance and investment*. Taylor & Francis Journals, Vol.9 (1), 33-44
- Hellen, K. and Caroline A., 2016. Effect of Debt Recovery Techniques on Performance of selected Financial Institutions in Eldoret Town. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*. Kisii University. Volume 5 Issue 10 October 2016 pp. 82-96
- Hoda, N. and Gupta, S. L., 2014. Loan Portfolio of a Faith - Based Microfinance Institution. *An Empirical Analysis*. Research Centre in Social and Humanistic Services.
- Umm al-Qura, Makkah, Saudi Arabia. Lumen Publishing House, Postmodern Openings, 2014, Vol. 5, Issue 1, pp. 65-94
- Jane, J. B. 2017. Effect of Liquidity on Financial Performance of Savings and Credit Societies in Kenya. *International journal of Finance* Vol. 2, Issue No.7, pp. 34-47,2017, CARI Journals, www.carijournal.org
- Khemraj, T. & Pasha, S., 2009. *The Determinants of Non-Performing Loans: An Econometric Case Study of Guyana*. New College of Gloria, University of Guyana. Available at: <https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/53128>
- Khieu, H. et al., 2012. The Determinants of Bank Loan Recovery rates. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, Vol. 36(4) pp 923-933. Elsevier.
- Kibrom, T. G., 2010. *Determinants of Successful Loan Repayment Performance of Private Borrowers in Development Bank of Ethiopia*, North Region, Makelle University, Ethiopia.
- Kibui, N. and Moronge, M., 2014. Effects of credit Risk Management on Financial Performance of SACCOs: A Case Study of Harambee SACCO. *International Academic Journal of Information Sciences and Project Management*, 1(3), 157-172 Jomo Kenyatta University
- Kinyera, R., 2014. *Causes of High Default Rate on Loans in Commercial Banks*. A case of Centenary Bank Ltd. Makerere University.
- Korankye, A. A., 2014. Causes and Control of Loan Default/Delinquency in Microfinance Institutions in Ghana. *American International Journal of Contemporary research* Vol. 4, No, 12, Centre for Promoting Ideas, USA

- Maina, E. et al., 2018. Effect of non-performing Loan Management Practices on Loan Recovery Performance of Deposit Taking Savings and Credit Cooperatives in Kenya. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. Vol 23, Issue 11, Ver 1 (Nov. 2018, 1-27
- Maithya, M.K., 2017. *Effect of Loan policies on Financial Performance of Church- based Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies in Kenya*. KCA University, Kenya
- Mariusz, G. et al., 2018. *Measuring expected time to default under stress conditions for corporate loans*. Springer. DOI: 10.1007/s 00181 – 018 – 1435 – 6.
- Miller, S., 2014. Risk Factors for Consumer Loan Default. A Censored Quartile Regression Analysis. University of Michigan.
- Mohd, N.S., 2013. *Repayment Performance in Microfinance Programs: An Individual Lending Approach*. University of Utara, Malaysia. Elsevier. pp. 489-496.
- Moody's Analytics., 2018. *Redefining Loan Monitoring and Early Warning Signals Detection Through an Integrated Solution*. Enterprise risk. <https://www.moody'sanalytics.com>
- Moronya, A.H., Onditi, A. and Nyangoi, A., 2016. Effect of Credit Risk Management Practices on the Financial Performance of SACCOs in Kisii County. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*. United Kingdom. Vol. IV, Issue 11, November 2016. pp. 612-632. Available at: <http://ijecm.co.uk/>
- Moti, H. O. et al. 2012. Effectiveness of Credit Management Systems on loans performance: Empirical evidence from micro finance Sector in Kenya. *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology*. Centre for Promoting Ideas, USA. Vol. 2 No. 6: October 2012
- Mphaka, P., 2017. *Strategies for Reducing Microfinance Loan Default in Low-Income Markets*. Walden University Scholar Works. Malawi Walden Dissertation and Doctoral Studies.
- Mpiira, S. et al., 2013. Factors influencing household participation in the Savings and Credit Cooperative (SACCO) programmes in Uganda. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. Vol. 8 (43): 5280 – 5288. Kampala, Uganda.
- Mugo, R. et al., 2015. Effect of Corporate Governance on Financial Performance of SACCOs in Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*. Egerton University. ISSN 2222-2847 (online). Vol. 6. No. 2, 2015; www.iiste.org
- Murthy, U. and Mariadas, P. A., 2017. An Exploratory Study on the factors contributing loan repayment default among the loan borrowers in microfinance Institutions in Shah Alam, Selangor. *International Journal of Business and Management* 12(12):242. Canadian Center of Science and Education.
- Mwangi, I. W. & Wanjau, K. L., 2013. The Role of SACCO in Growth of Youth Entrepreneurship in Kenya: A Case of Nairobi County. *Greener Journal of Business and Management Studies* Vol.3 (3), pp113-118, April 2013. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.
- Mwangi, M. J., 2013. Credit Monitoring and Recovery Strategies Adopted by Commercial Banks in Kenya. University of Nairobi. Nairobi, Kenya. pp. 11-13
- Nawai N. and Mohd, N.S., 2013. *Loan Repayment Problems in Microfinance Programs that use Individual Lending Approach: A Qualitative Analysis*. College of Business, University Utara Malaysia, 06010 Sintok, Kedah. Elsevier
- Ndiege, O.B. et al., 2016. The Link between Financial Performance and Loan Repayment Management in Tanzanian SACCOs. *African Journal of Business Management*, Moshi Co-operative University, Moshi, Tanzania. Academic journals Vol. 10(4), pp. 89-97
- Neuberger, L., Lukas, M., Ornsiri, R., 2011. Collateral and its substitutes in Emerging Markets' Lending. *Journal of Banking and Finance* 36(2012) 817-834, Elsevier

- Nguta, M. H. and Huka, G. S., 2013. Factors Influencing loan repayment Default in Microfinance Institutions. The experience of Imenti North District, Kenya. *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology*. Meru University of science and Technology. Centre for Promoting Ideas, USA. Vol. 3 No. 3, March 2013. pp.80-84
- Nkundabanyanga, S. K. et al., 2014. Lending terms, Financial Literacy and Formal Credit Accessibility. *International Journal of Social Economics* May 2014. Imerald Group Publishing Ltd. DOI:10.1108/IJSE – 03 – 2013-0075
- Nuwagaba, A., 2012. Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies (SACCOs) As a Source of Financing Agriculture. Challenges and Lessons Learnt. *Journal of Environmental and Earth Science*. Vol. 2, No.11, 2012 (Online). www.iiste.org
- Nzomo, S. M., 2017. The Effect of Multiple Borrowings on Financial Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Machachos town. University of Nairobi.
- Okiror, W., 2018. *Digitisation of SACCOs in Uganda - Drivers and Impact Study*. Asigma Advisory Report. Mercy Corps. [available@http://fsduganda.or.ug/finscope-2018-survey-report](http://fsduganda.or.ug/finscope-2018-survey-report).
- Okori, A., 2018. Poor Management Upsetting SACCOs- *The New Vision* Oct 19, 2018.
- Omeke, M. et al., 2019. The relationship between complexity behaviour and Enterprise Growth. A case of savings and credit co-operatives in Uganda. *Cogent Business and management*. Taylor & Francis. Volume 6, 2919- Issue 1
- Opala, J. A., 2014. Effect of Financial Stability on the Performance of Deposit Taking SACCOs in Nairobi County, Kenya.
- Patience, C. M. et al., 2016. The Effectiveness of Commercial Banks' Credit Appraisal Techniques in Improving Asset Quality. *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance*, Vol. 7, Issue 5, Version 1 pp. 63-78, www.iosrjournal.org
- Riza, E. et al., 2015. Evaluating Credit Risk and Loan Performance in on line Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Lending. *Applied Economics* 47(1), 54-70, 2015. Taylor & Francis.
- Rodrigues, I. B. et al., 2017. *Development and Validation of a New Tool to Measure the facilitators, barriers and preferences to exercise in people with Osteoporosis*. University of Waterloo. BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders (2017) 18:540. Springer.
- Schicks, J., 2011. Over indebtedness of Micro borrowers in Ghana, *An Empirical Study from a Customer Protection Perspective*. Universite' Libre de Bruxelles. Centre for Financial Inclusion at ACCION International, Publication No.15
- Sheila, A. L., 2011. *Lending Methodologies and loan losses and default in a Microfinance deposit-taking institutions in Uganda*. A case study of Finca Uganda Kabale Branch (MDI). Makerere University, Uganda.
- Shu-Teng, L. et al. 2015. Determinants of Microfinance Repayment Performance: Evidence from Small Medium Enterprises in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*; Vol. 7, No. 11; 2015. Universiti Putra Malaysia. Canadian Center of Science and Education. Available at: www.ccsenet.org/ijef
- Ssekiziyivu, B., Bananuka, J., Nabeta, I. N., Tumwebaze, Z., 2017. Borrowers' Characteristics, Credit Terms and Loan Repayment Performance Among Clients of Microfinance Institutions. Evidence From Rural Uganda. *Journal of Economics and International Finance* Vol.10 (1), pp. 1-10, Makerere University Business School.
- Ssekiziyivu, B. et al., 2017. Credit Allocation, Risk Management and Loan Portfolio Performance of MFIs – A Case of Ugandan firms. *Cogent Business & Management*, 4:1, 1374921, DOI:10.1080/23311975.2017.1374921. *CrossMark*.
- Tijjani, I., 2016. The Moderating Role of Loan Monitoring on the Relationship between Macroeconomic variables and non-performing loans in Association of Southeast Asian Nations Countries. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 2016, 6(2), 402-408. Ahmadu Bello University

- Twesige, D., 2021. *Causes of Loan Defaults Within Microfinance Institutions: Learning From Micro and Small Business owners in Rwanda. A Case of MSEs in Kigali*. University of Rwanda. April 2021. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/Publication/350660878>.
- Ursachi, G., Loana, A. H., Zait, A., 2013. How reliable are measurement scales? *External factors with indirect influence on reliability estimators*. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 20 (2015) pp. 679 – 686. Elsevier
- Wilson S., 2007. A Causal Framework for Credit Default Theory. University of Technology Sydney, *SSRN Electronic journal*. Quantitative Finance Research Centre. Online: www.qfrc.uts.edu.au
- Yong, Y. and Mwase, N., 2012. *BRIC's Approaches to development financing and their implications for LICs* (IMF Working Paper) Volume 1, Issue 4, June, 2012.
- Zainuddin, M. and Yasin, I.M., 2019. *Loan Delinquency in Microfinance: Does it have any Relationship with Poverty Level of Borrowers?* International Conference on Business, Accounting, Finance and Economics 2019. Universiti Tunku Abdul Rahman (UTAR), Kampar, Perak, Malaysia. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336287478>

Simplicity, Moderation and Sensitization as Preventive Measures to Excessive Alcohol Intake and Intra-Religious Conflicts in the African Context

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Abstract:

The relationship between alcohol consumption and conflicts has been explored in several contexts. Little research has been conducted on the subject in Wa. The purpose of this research is to explore the relationship between alcohol consumption and conflicts where alcohol consumption is on the increase. A quantitative research design is used to collect data from both primary and secondary sources for analysis using sphinx IQ software. Some questionnaires were used for data collection. The results show that alcohol consumption is associated with religious conflicts. It is suggested that consumers should adopt simplicity and moderation habits, while manufacturers and sellers should provide quality products and a sustainable sensitization to reduce alcohol abuse and conflictual situations.

Keywords: Alcohol consumption, religious conflicts, Christians, Muslims, Traditionalists.

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol is used as a beverage in normal daily activities across the world (Bazié, 2011 ; Nassè, 2018). It is also used in some religious activities as well as social functions (Dumbili, 2013 ; Porter, 2013 ; Nassè et al., 2019). In fact the alcohol industry has become one of the largest sectors of production in the world. However, research has shown that alcohol consumption has diverse effects on consumers, including conflicts. Research on alcohol consumption and conflicts has been done in many parts of the world including Africa (Valentine et al., 2010 ; Amankwaa et al., 2012 ; Dery & Diedong, 2014 ; Nassè et al. 2016). Ghana is one of the most alcohol consuming country in the West African region, after Nigeria and Ivory Coast (Ritchie & Roser, 2020). This is an indication that alcohol plays a very important role in the lives of the people in Ghana. While alcohol consumption may be widespread, certain factors such as culture, distance and time might moderate its prevalence rate in society (Adoma & Darko, 2020). Much of the literature on the effects of alcohol is dedicated to other effects of the substance. However, there is emerging literature that confirms some relationship between alcohol consumption and violent conflicts in intimate relationships (Murphy et al., 2005, Dery & Diedong 2014). There is not much work done on alcohol consumption and conflicts in the context of Wa. In the same vein, no work has concurrently shown one's level of alcohol consumption on religious conflicts. In addition, there is no a clear policy by governmental authorities, sellers and manufacturer that helps to minimize or eradicate alcohol related conflicts in the religious scenery. This research is to fill these research gaps.

Thus, the main objective of this research is to examine the association between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Economic Theory of Consumption

These theorists argument state that consumers purchase decisions, and consumption decisions rely on some economic criteria (Ouédraogo, 2007), Kitchathorn (2009), Nassè (2019). Thus, some economic criteria such as the purchasing power, the consumer income also take into consideration that some emotional factors may affect consumption. In reality, the institution of the private property state with the emergence of entrepreneurial capitalism and free market systems has led to a natural imposition of economic class realism that regulates individual taste, purchasing power, purchasing decisions and choices.

The Research Concepts

The research aims to define the concepts that are in line with the topic.

The Concept of Conflict

The concept of conflict has been defined by several authors. In the western context, Goodhand and Hume (2009) have defined conflict as a disagreement resulting from individuals or groups that differ in behavior, beliefs, and values or in needs. The concept of conflict as approached by Goodhand and Hume is limited by the fact that it does not involve the violent aspect of conflict, but it rather shows conflict to be a mere disagreement. In the African context, Nasse et al. (2016) have approached the concept of conflict in a religious environment, as a misunderstanding between individuals and groups due to a given misbehavior that affect a given religious community or group. The concept of conflict as approached by Nasse et al. (2016) depicts the social violence aspect of conflict and that is why recommendations have drawn the attention of political authorities and managers to help prevent these conflicts. In Ghana, Awedoba (2012) has defined the concept of conflict as a relationship between two or more parties centered on differences, disagreement and some issues of common interest or concern.

Alcohol Consumption

Alcohol consumption problems are a global phenomenon, and its nature is very complex. The predisposition to alcohol abuse differs significantly from one distinct person to another and from one country to another. Alcohol consumption is contingent on the accessibility of alcohol, the nation's guidelines related to alcohol, the country's social and cultural background, religious tradition and its economics situation (Chen, & Yin, 2008).

The pervasiveness of alcohol dependency also differs from one ethnic or traditional group to another (Chen, & Yin, 2008). For instance, in Ghana some ethnic groups and religious groups consume alcohol whilst others do not consume it. It is clear that natural disasters, religious conflicts, ethnic conflicts as well as political disputes do have made it impossible for some people to assess some opportunities in many countries.

For Amankwaa, Reed, and Owens (2012), alcohol consumption is the intake of industrial alcoholic beverages. In Africa and particularly in West Africa, it is agreed by the research of Nassè et al. (2016) that the concept of alcohol consumption is also the drinking of industrial alcoholic drinks. Still, in the context of Burkina Faso, Bazié (2011) has approached the concept of alcohol consumption to be the drinking of traditional alcoholic beverages, in his study on understanding communication in the traditional environment, and the sociocultural characteristics of different ethnic groups.

Research Hypotheses

From the literature review above the alternative hypothesis and the null hypothesis have been constructed as follows :

- ▶ **H_a** : There is a relationship between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts.
- ▶ **H_o** : There is not a relationship between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts.

Research Model

Figure 1-Research Model
(Source: adapted from Nassè, 2019)

MATERIALS AND METHOD.

Epistemological Posture

This is a quantitative research focused on postpositivist posture.

Research Procedures

The quantitative sampling strategy consists of using a random sampling technique combined with the snowballing technique due to a lack of time and an insufficiency of resources. The questionnaire is pre-tested with the consumers of alcoholic beverages. This first test is done on a sample of 10 respondents. The pre-test results are used to draft a final version of the questionnaire. The designed questionnaire is administered again to the consumers. This sample is a subset of the studied population. To set the sample size, the following mathematic formula is used: $n = (p)(1-p) / (e / Z)^2$, where p represents the selected proportion of an attribute, for example gender. Here, assuming 50-50 female to male ratio, $p=0.50$ or 50%; e represents the level of precision or accuracy set for this research, here 5%, and Z is the number related to the degree of confidence, and in this case $Z=1.96$ or 95% confidence (Ganassali, 2009: 51; Hejase and Hejase, 2013: 231). Then, in this case, the formula becomes: $n = (0.5 \times (1-0.5)) / (e / 1.96)^2 = 0.25 / (e / 1.96)^2$. The number of people to interview for a maximum error of 6.0%, then is $n = 0.25 / (0.06 / 1.96)^2 = 267$ people. A sample of 267 people is enough for a 6-point error estimate. Once the sample is determined, data collection is done through a questionnaire on a paper and it is filled by alcohol consumers. The total number of respondents is 308. Research context. The country where the research is conducted is Ghana. The research area includes the city of Wa.

Research Participants

Participants are Christian, Muslim, and Traditional who consume alcohol, and who have consumed alcohol for at least two years. They are considered using the following criteria that include age, sex, religion, educational level, marital status, occupation, and social class. First, the age of participants ranges from 18 to 45 years old and above. Second, the gender of the

participants includes men and women. Third, the educational level of participants includes illiterates, and those with primary school, secondary school or university levels.

Research Context

The research is carried out in the main regional city of Upper West that is Wa. The research period is two and half years. It has started before the covid-19 crisis, and as it has continued during the covid-19 crisis.

Data Analysis.

In this research, the quantitative data is analysed using the quantitative version of Sphinx IQ. The quantitative data is computed into the quantitative version of Sphinx IQ and then the statistical data such as descriptive statistics and correlations are generated.

Ethical Implications

In this research, there are some ethical measures to be taken into account as what is normal to be considered for a scientific research (Creswell, 2009). In this research in order to increase participation, respondents are not requested to give their names, and information given by the respondents is kept confidential (Nassè, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The statistical data about the different respondents is summarized in Table 1

Table 1 Statistical data of the respondents

Religious affiliation	Number of respondents	Percentage
Christians	224	72.7%
Muslims	12	3.9%
Traditionalists	72	23.4%
Total	308	100%

Alcohol Consumption and Religious Conflicts

Table 2 Relationships between 'Alcohol consumption' and 'Religious conflicts'

Variable crossing	Results
"Alcohol consumption" and "Religious conflicts"	$p = < 0.01$; 108.67 ; dof = 11. The relationship is very significant.

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

H_a : There is an association between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts.

H_o : There is not an association between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts.

For the hypothesis testing, the correlation between the variable 'Alcohol consumption' and 'Religious conflicts' is the method used. The p-value $p = < 0.01$, the Chi-square value $\chi^2 = 108.67$, and the degree of freedom $dof = 11$ are found to be significant (as indicated on the above Table 1). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is confirmed.

H_a : There is an association between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts.

DICUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Alcohol Consumption and Religious Conflicts

Some researchers underline in their studies the relationships between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts in different context (Murphy & al., 2005; Nassè, 2019; Nassè, Ouédraogo & Diop, 2016) with influence of some factors such as extreme poverty, business relationships, culture with Christian respondents. The present research depicts the same relationship between alcohol consumption and religious conflicts in the Ghanaian context with a particular concern on Christians, Muslims and Animists. Observation has shown that in the Ghanaian context the weight of Christian beliefs and Islamic beliefs affect both tradition and the consumption of alcohol. These religious beliefs are strengthened by some strong moral values that are strongly inculcated through education in school (Nassè, 2020).

The covid-19 crisis has some sensitive effects on consumption (Davis, 2021), on alcohol consumption and thus, on religious conflicts. The observation is that with crisis some consumers have been in desperation and they drink a lot of alcohol to forget their daily challenges what enhance conflictual situations and especially household conflicts and religious conflicts.

CONCLUSION

The present research shows that alcohol consumption influences religious conflicts in a particular context.

Contributions

There are some conceptual contributions that enrich the literature as the constructs of alcohol consumption and religious conflicts are redefined in a specific context. In terms of theoretical contributions, it also enriches the cultural theories on consumption in a new context, where there is a combination of multiple factors that moderate alcohol consumption.

In terms of managerial contributions, it is imperative for manufacturers to have a responsible advertising policy towards alcohol consumers by recommending moderation and simplicity in their consumption habits. Manufacturers and sellers should provide quality products to consumers, in addition to sustainable and responsible sensitization campaigns that takes into account their health concern. It is clear that consumers that are healthy can still purchase and consume alcohol. However, consumers with health related problems might not purchase and might not consume alcohol beverages what could reduce income for manufacturers. It is also good for religious leaders to sensitize consumers to have responsible and ethical consumption habits.

Future Research

Research observations have shown that there are less ethical concern in terms of consumption, thus, it is necessary to investigate ethical issues and consumption habits in the West African context

Conflict of Interests

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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REFERENCES

- Adoma, V. & Darko, M. A. (2020). The impact of alcoholic beverage advertisement on student's purchasing behaviour at Sunyani technical university. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 26(2): 26-42.
- Aasoglenang, T. A., & Baataar, C. (2012). Decentralized planning for pre-conflict and post-conflict management in the Bawku municipal assembly of Ghana. *Ghana Journal of Development Studies*, 9(2), 63-79.
- Alam, S.S., Mohd, R., & Hisham, B. (2011). Is religiosity an important determinant on Muslim consumer behaviour in Malaysia? *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 2(1), 83-96.
- Al-Hyari, K., M., Alnsour, G., Al-Weshah, & Haffar, M. (2012). Religious beliefs and consumer behaviour: from loyalty to boycotts. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 3(2), 155-174.
- Amankwaa, A. A., W., Reed, & Owens, De' A. (2012). Church attendance and alcohol consumption level: reasons for not drinking alcohol among college students. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(4), 1-8.
- Andaleeb, S. S. (1993). Religious affiliations and consumer behavior: an examination of hospitals. *Journal of Health Care Marketing*, 13(4), 42-49.
- Anderson, D. R., Sweeney, D. J., Williams, T. A., Camm, J. D., & Cochran, J. J. (2015). *Statistiques pour l'économie et la gestion*. (5^{ème} éd.). Paris, PA: Distribution Nouveaux Horizons.
- Awedoba, A. K. (2011). *An ethnographic study of Northern Ghanaian conflicts: towards sustainable peace*. Accra, AC: Sub-Saharan Publishers.
- Bailey, J. M., and Sood, J. (1993). The effect of religious affiliation on consumer behavior: a preliminary investigation. *Journal of Managerial*, 3(5), 328-352.
- Bagozzi, R., Abe, S., Wong, N., & Bergami, M. (2000). Cultural and situational contingencies and the theory of reasoned action: application to fast food restaurant consumption. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 92(2), 97-106.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. New Jersey, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Banyte, J., & Matulioniene, L. (2005). The singularities of the cultural element in consumer behavior. *Innovative Marketing*, 1(1), 33-39.
- Bazié, J. (2011). *Comprendre la communication en milieu traditionnel*. Ouagadougou, OR : Les Presses Africaines.
- Benabdallah, M., & Jolibert, A. (2013). L'acculturation : l'influence des sous-cultures d'origine et de la distance culturelle. *Décisions Marketing*, 72(1), 179-205.
- Berger, A. (1997). Population, consumption, and the environment: religious and secular responses. *Journal of Hindu-Christian Studies*, 10(2), 2-4.
- Bidan, M. (2010). Systèmes d'information et développement durable : modèles théoriques et pratiques organisationnelles. *Management et Avenir*, 9(39), 304-306.
- Bourgoin, H., (1984). *L'Afrique malade du management*. Paris, PA : J. Picollec.
- Campanella, M. R. (2016). *Halal food consumption, responsibility, moral overtones and re-negotiation of categories among Muslim believers in Stockholm County*. Uppsala, UP: University of Uppsala.
- Chen, C. C., & Yin, S. J. (2008). Alcohol abuse and related factors in Asia. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 20(5), 425-433.
- Cleveland, M., Laroche, M., & Hallab, R. (2010). *Globalization, culture, religion, and values: comparing consumption patterns of Lebanese Muslims and Christians*. Ontario, ON: University of Western Ontario.

- Cole, H. (2015). Factors influencing the association between religiosity and drinking behavior in underage college students. *University of Kentucky, Theses and Dissertations-Psychology*, 54(1), 1-48.
- Coyne, I. T. (1997). Sampling in qualitative research. Purposeful and theoretical sampling: merging or clear boundaries? *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 26(1), 623-630.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approach*. California, CA: Sage Publication.
- Davis, G. (2021). The many ways COVID-19 affects households: consumption, time, and health outcomes. *Rev Econ Household* 19, 281–289.
- De Mooij, M. (2003). Convergence and divergence in consumer behaviour: implications for global advertising. *International Journal of Advertising*, 22(2), 183-202.
- Dery, I., & Diedong, A. L. (2014). Domestic violence against women in Ghana: an exploratory study in Upper West Region, Ghana. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(12), 228-244.
- Diop, F. (2004). *L'achat familial en Afrique*. Dakar, DA : École Supérieure Polytechnique de Dakar, Université Cheikh Anta Diop.
- Diop, F. (2012). *L'influence de la religion musulmane sur le comportement de consommation au Sénégal*. Dakar, DA : École Supérieure Polytechnique de Dakar, Université Cheikh Anta Diop.
- Dollard, J., Miller, N. E., Doob, L. W., Mowrer, O. H., & Sears, R. R. (1939). *Frustration and aggression*. New Haven, NH: Yale University Press.
- Dumbili, E. (2013). Changing patterns of alcohol consumption in Nigeria: an exploration of responsible factors and consequences. *A Journal of the BSA MedSoc Group* 7(1):20-33.
- Durmaz, Y., Reyhan, O., & Mücahit, C. (2011). The impact of cultural factors on the consumer buying behaviors examined through an empirical study. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(5), 109-114.
- Essoo, N., & Dibb, S. (2004). Religious influences on shopping behaviour: an exploratory study. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 20(7/8), 683-712.
- Fam, K. S., Waller, D. S., & Erdogan, B. Z. (2002). The influence of religion on attitudes towards the advertising of controversial products. *European Journal of Marketing*, 38(5/6), 537-555.
- Fred-Mensah, B. K. (2005). Ideas, power, and multilateral institutions. *International Studies Review*, 7(1), 84-86.
- Ganassali, S. (2009). *Les enquêtes par questionnaires avec sphinx*. Paris, PA : Pearson Éducation.
- Ger, G. (2005). Religion and consumption: the profane sacred. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 32(44), 79-81.
- Heiman, A., Zilberman, D., & Gordon B. (2001). Religion, religiosity, lifestyles and food consumption. *Agribusiness, an International Journal*, 17(4), 455-468.
- Hejase A. J. & Hejase H. J. (2013). *Research methods, a practical approach for business students (Second ed.)*. Philadelphia, PH : Masadir Inc.
- Institut national de la statistique et de la démographie*, (2010). Recensement général de la population et de l'habitat 2006, rapport définitif, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.
- Jung, K., & Kau, A. K. (2004). Culture's influence on consumer behaviors: differences among ethnic groups in a multiracial Asian country. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 31(1), 366-372.

- Khalla, S. (2006). *Relation au sacré et fidélité à la marque. Thèse de Doctorat ès Sciences de Gestion*. Caen, CA : Université de Caen.
- Kibora, L. (2015). Social change, new food habits and food price volatility in Burkina Faso. *IDS Bulletin*, 46(6), 105-109.
- Kitchathorn, P. (2009). *Factor influencing customer repurchase intention: an investigation of switching barriers that influence the relationship between satisfaction and repurchase intention in the low-cost airlines industry in Thailand*. Adelaide, AD: University of South Australia.
- Kunfaa, E. Y. (1996). *Sustainable rural health services through community-based organisations: women's groups Ghana*. Dortmund, DO: Spring Research Series No. 16, University of Dortmund.
- Le Petit Larousse Illustré, (2006). *Langue : français*. Paris, PA: Éditions Larousse.
- Livian, Y. F., & Shamba, P. B. (2014). *Le management africain introuvable : pour une approche de l'hybridité segmentée*. Marseille, MA : Communication pour la 4ème Conférence Atlas-AFMI.
- Lord, R. K., & Putrevu, M. (2005). Religious influence on consumer behavior: classification and measurement. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 32(184), 651-652.
- Marfo, S., & Musah, H. (2018). Examining the position of the chieftaincy institution in modern political system of Ghana. *Journal of Sociology and Social Work*, 6(1), 64-72.
- Mansori, S. (2012). Impact of religion affiliation and religiosity on consumer innovativeness: the evidence of Malaysia. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 17(3), 301-307.
- Marshall, M. N. (1996). Sampling for qualitative research. *Family Practice*, 13(6), 522-525.
- Mokhlis, S. (2006). The effect of religiosity on shopping orientation: an exploratory study in Malaysia. *The Journal of American Academy of Business*, 9(1), 64-74.
- Mokhlis, S. (2008). Consumer religiosity and the importance of store attributes. *The Journal of Human Resource and Adult Learning*, 4(2), 122-133.
- Mokhlis, S. (2009). Relevancy and measurement of religiosity in consumer behavior research. *International Business Research, Management Trade*, 2(3), 75-84.
- Mokhlis, S. (2010). Religious contrasts in consumer shopping styles: a factor analytic comparison. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 2(1), 52-64.
- Morse, J. M. (1991). *Strategies for sampling in qualitative nursing research: a contemporary dialogue*. California, CA: Sage.
- Morsy, S., & Néji, B. (2016). Innovativité et religiosité : cas de la consommation alimentaire en Tunisie. *Proceedings of the Marketing Spring Colloquy (MSC), Unit of Research & Applications in Marketing (URAM)* 7(1), 193-212.
- Murphy, C. M., Winters, J., O'Farrell, T. J., Fals-Stewart, W., & Murphy, M. (2005). Alcohol consumption and intimate partner violence by alcoholic men: Comparing violent and nonviolent conflicts. *Psychology of Addictive Behaviors*, 19(1), 35-42. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0893-164X.19.1.35>
- Mustafar, M. Z., & Borhan, J. T. (2013). Muslim consumer behavior: emphasis on ethics from Islamic perspective. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 9(18), 1301-1307.
- Nassè, B. T. (2006). *Kasim borrowings from English: an evidence from Burkina Faso. A master thesis*. Ouagadougou, OU: University of Ouagadougou.

- Nassè, B. T. (2012). *How to succeeding in Church missionarial work in West Africa*. Saarbrücken, SA: Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Nassè, B. T. (2016). L'équité interne dans la gestion de la relation client : une étude comparative quantitative de trois entreprises privées du Burkina Faso. Université Aube Nouvelle, *Journal Ouest-Africain des Sciences de Gestion*, 1(1), 38 -54.
- Nassè, B. T., Ouédraogo, A. & Diop, F. (2016). L'influence de la religiosité sur les comportements des consommateurs à l'égard des boissons industrielles non alcoolisées : une étude quantitative et une étude qualitative portant sur les musulmans dans le contexte du Burkina Faso. *Journal Ouest Africain de Sciences de Gestion*, 1(2), 1-28.
- Nassè, B. T. (2018). *Pratiques religieuses et comportement de consommation dans un contexte africain : une étude exploratoire sur les consommateurs au Burkina Faso*. Thèse de Doctorat en sciences de Gestion, spécialité marketing. Ouagadougou, OR: Université Aube nouvelle en cotutelle avec l'Université Cheikh Anta Diop.
- Nassè, B. T., Ouédraogo, A. & Diop, F. (2019). Religiosity and consumer behavior in developing countries : An exploratory study on Muslims in the context of Burkina Faso. *African Journal of Business Management*, 13(4), 116-127.
- Nassè, B. T. (2020). Excessive alcohol consumption and conflicts : an exploratory study of Christian groups in ouagadougou (Burkina Faso). Wa : University of Development Studies.
- Nayeem, T. (2012). Cultural influences on consumer behavior. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(21), 79-91.
- Nurbasari, A. (2015). The impact of spiritual marketing on consumer behavior in choosing halal food: case study on moslim community in Bandung. *Al Hijaz International Refereed Journal for Islamic and Arabic Studies*, 273(10), 271-306.
- Ouédraogo, A. (2007). Strategic management in African firms: a local perspective. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 5(1), 82-94.
- Patel, M. (2010). Influence of religion on shopping behaviour of consumers-an exploratory study. *National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Commerce and Management*, 1(5), 68-78.
- Picard-Masson, M. (2014). Les liens entre la consommation de boissons énergisantes et la consommation de psychotropes chez les jeunes : que connaissons-nous du phénomène ? *Drogues, Santé et Société*, 13(2), 1-25.
- Porter, C. (2013). *The religion of consumption and Christian neighbor love*. Chicago, CH: Loyola University.
- Quivy, R., & Van Campenhoudt, L. (2011). *Manuel de recherche en sciences sociales* (2^{ème} éd.). Paris, PA: Dunod.
- Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2020). "Alcohol Consumption". Published online at OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: '<https://ourworldindata.org/alcohol-consumption>' [Online Resource]
- Roche, D. (2009). *Rédiger son mémoire avec succès*. Paris, PA: Eyrolles, Éditions d'Organisation.
- Ruzeviciute, R., & Ruzevicius, J. (2011). Consumption culture in the presence of globalisation: the influence of religion, nation and ethnicity on consumption patterns. *Ekonomika*, 90(4), 150-163.
- Sow, D. M. (2005). *Alimentation et boissons au Burkina Faso : au-delà de la survie*. Genève, GE : Bureau International du Travail. Suisse.
- The United Bible Society, (1994). *Good news Bible*. New York, NY : Bible Societies, Harper Collins.
- Usinier, J. C. (2000). *Marketing across cultures* (3rd ed.). London, LO: Pearson Education.

Valentine, G., Jayne, M., Gould, M., & Keenan, J. (2010). Family life and alcohol consumption: A study of the transmission of drinking practices. *Joseph Rowntree Foundation*, 1(1), 4-59.

Van Den Bergh, J., & Nijkamp, P. (1991). Operationalizing sustainable development: dynamic ecological economic models. *Ecological Economics*, 4(1), 11-33.

Van Laethem, N., & Body, L. (2008). *Le plan marketing* (2^{ème} éd.). Paris, PA: Dunod.

Other Statistical Details
Table 2 Respondents' age

Age	Number of respondents	Percentage
10 - 25 years old	83	26.9%
26-35 years old	129	41.9%
36- 45 years old	84	27.3%
46- and above	12	3.9%
Total	308	100%

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

Table 3 Respondents' profession

Profession	Number of respondents	Percentage
Public employee	06	1.9%
Private employee	230	74.7%
unemployed	72	23.4%
Total	308	100%

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

Table 4 Respondents' social status

Social status	Number of respondents	Percentage
Very poor	6	1.9%
Poor	147	47.7%
Rich	149	48.4%
Very rich	6	1.9%
Total	308	100%

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

Table 5 Respondents' gender

Gender	Number of respondents	Percentage
Female	29	09.4%
Male	279	90.6%
Total	308	100%

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

Table 6 Respondents' marital status

Marital status	Number of respondents	Percentage
Single	141	45.8%
Engaged	68	22.1%
Married	93	30.2%
Divorced	06	1.9%

Total	308	100%
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(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

Table 5 Respondents' level of education

Level of education	Number of respondents	Percentage
Illiterate	79	25.6%
Primary school	60	19.5%
Secondary school	95	30.8%
University	74	24%
Total	308	100%

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

Table 6 Respondents' level of education

Residence	Number of respondents	Percentage
Wa town	302	98.1%
Other areas	06	1.9%
Total	308	100%

(Source : fieldwork, 2019)

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Conflict of Interest Statement

No conflict of interest